

IMPROVED TRANSDISCIPLINARY
SCIENCE FOR EFFECTIVE
ECOSYSTEM-BASED MARITIME
SPATIAL PLANNING AND
CONSERVATION IN EUROPEAN
SEAS

Deliverable D4.2

Report on the barriers to adopting novel
and dynamic approaches to Marine
Protected Areas designation and
implementation

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Executive Summary

One of today's most pressing challenges is to safeguard the loss of ecosystem biodiversity and functioning, while simultaneously allowing for their exploitation by those who depend on their services, goods and benefits. In Europe, Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) is the main governance process to ideally integrate sustainability and exploitation. This requires tools and knowledge to align MSP and Marine Protected Area (MPA) designation processes. However, the degree to which these management approaches have been successfully aligned and integrated is debatable. Similarly, the ability of European governance regimes to adapt their utilisation of MSP and MPA processes in the wake of institutional and environmental change is uncertain. Whilst Deliverable 4.1 presented an institutional and policy audit of each Planning Site, the purpose of this report, Deliverable 4.2 (D4.2), is to demonstrate the adaptive capacity of governance regimes. This is achieved by assessing how change and learning occur across governance processes. D4.2 then concludes by considering what these findings reveal about the factors that enable and prevent adaptive capacity. This Deliverable will provide vital information to guide how MarinePlan co-develops with stakeholders a Decision Support System (DSS) for [Ecosystem-Based Maritime Spatial Planning](#) (EB-MSP). Additionally, D4.2 will combine with Work Package 4's final task, Task 4.3, to inform the development of best practice guidance regarding the enhancement of the effectiveness of spatial conservation and restoration measures for marine biodiversity in European Seas.

The task that informs D4.2, Task 4.2, involved an examination of how the governance regimes of MarinePlan's eight Planning Sites use diverse knowledge on conservation measures and MSP processes. This task included a review of the policy discourses through which MPAs become prioritised, leading to the identification of dominant discourses that influence the development and implementation of new approaches. Document reviews of relevant reports and publications, added to in-depth semi-structured interviews with a broad range of marine stakeholders, were used to inform Task 4.2's analysis. This analysis is presented in D4.2, with the following sections revealing insight into stakeholders' perceptions of existing governance regimes, their opinions of what change is required to governance processes, examples of how change is advocated for, and a demonstration of how successful such advocacy has been. Information is also presented on learning and change within the governance network, with the 'multi-level learning loop' model being used to interpret the adaptive capacity of each Planning Site's governance regimes. Insight into the impediments that are hindering change, learning and the implementation of novel management approaches are also presented.

Key trends regarding governance problems across the Planning Sites include limited resource capacity to conduct key governance tasks, instances of bias and power imbalances within participation processes, policy complexity, low levels of transboundary cooperation, and 'silo thinking' across government departments. Advocacy approaches vary across the Planning Sites, with some cases of coalitions being developed between environmental Non-Government Organisations (eNGOs) and marine sectors. There is also evidence of advocacy being conducted via environmental campaigns, working groups and committees, and the implementation of formal partnerships between eNGOs and governments. More innovative approaches to advocacy include eNGOs taking legal proceedings against governments for their inaction and failure to maintain legislative objectives. By presenting examples of change and learning across the governance regimes of each Planning Site, information regarding the adaptive capacity of the regions is demonstrated. This includes instances of single-loop learning, such as reactionary policy changes and the implementation of new measures to address emergent problems. There are multiple examples of double-loop learning, including the revision of MSP and MPA processes, the implementation of new technologies, the creation

of formal networks, and the development of a range of alternative means of marine protection. Instances of triple-loop learning are less common across the regions, yet some examples are demonstrated. In the Bay of Biscay, there is evidence of the governance regime transforming to enable MPAs co-development. A shift toward fisheries co-management has been supported in parts of the Southern North Sea site. In the Western Mediterranean Sea, governance systems have facilitated bottom-up approaches to the creation of Fisheries Restricted Areas, whereby stakeholders have been empowered to instigate management change. Challenges to facilitating further change remain, such as limited political will, a lack of long-term objectives, limited transboundary integration, path-dependency in policy frameworks, eNGO fatigue, and undetermined approaches for managing new marine sectors.

The findings presented in D4.2 demonstrate some of the key barriers and enablers to adaptive capacity. Barriers include hierarchical and top-down policy processes, short-term and unstable political frameworks, limited stakeholder and sector inclusion in the design, implementation and management of governance activities, 'silo thinking' and fragmented communication across governance networks, and rigid or outdated policy and bureaucratic systems. Enablers include clear institutional and legislative frameworks, regional-national-international policy integration, transboundary cooperation, inter-organisational networks, formal partnerships between stakeholders, sectors and government, measurable targets and implementable goals, the training of governmental staff, and available financing for trialling innovative solutions. By assessing these factors, it is evident that informed decision-making, transparency and the prioritisation of prioritisation are key elements of adaptive governance. The findings of this report clarify how all network actors – government, stakeholders and sectors – play a crucial role in enabling adaptation. Therefore, regimes need to focus on developing greater interaction with non-state actors and facilitate their engagement in MSP and MPA process design, implementation and management. It is concluded that successful transitions to adaptive marine governance across the Planning Sites will depend on the development of tailored and context-specific co-management approaches.

The findings of this report will directly inform the remaining task (Task 4.3) of Work Package 4 – which will develop realistic and implementable policy recommendations to improve the science-base for EB-MSP – as well as other MarinePlan activities. By demonstrating how adaptive capacity varies across institutional contexts, the policy recommendations and solutions proposed by MarinePlan can be tailored to match the individual conditions of each Planning Site. Key solutions include the need to foster political commitment to change, a shift toward reflexive governance – wherein multi-level and network learning is vital – and the creation of formal collaboration partnerships. D4.2 represents not only a valuable assessment of existing governance regimes across multiple European regions but also a vital resource that will help to inform the development of MarinePlan's practical outputs.

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1. Introduction

The sustainable governance of marine resources has been a topic of continued concern (Alexander et al., 2018; Elliott et al., 2023; Stead, 2019). Prevailing management approaches have tended to be technocratic, largely neglecting complexity and the human dimension (Bennett, 2019; McKinley et al., 2020; Saunders et al., 2019). This has led to critical arguments being made for major paradigm shifts in the design and implementation of marine management (Evans et al., 2023; Flannery et al., 2016; Kelly et al., 2018; van Assche et al., 2020). Attention has moved towards an improvement of our comprehension of the factors required for sustainable marine governance in changing environments, with adaptive governance and social learning identified as essential for governing social-ecological systems during periods of abrupt change (Dutra et al., 2019; Greenhill et al., 2020; Österblom et al., 2013). Adaptive capacity is defined as “*the ability of a resource governance system to first alter processes and if required convert structural elements as response to experienced or expected changes in the societal or natural environment*” (Pahl-Wostl, 2009: 355). The ability of governance systems to deal with uncertainty and surprise is an essential requirement for their sustainability. This is particularly the case in times of increasing uncertainty due to climate and global change (Hurlbert and Gupta, 2016; Renn and Klinke, 2014). However, knowledge about the relationship between the characteristics of marine governance regimes, their performance and the nature of their dynamics, requires continued examination. Learning from the concept of multi-level ‘loop learning’ (see Löf, 2013; Medema et al., 2014; Pahl-Wostl, 2009), this report demonstrates an approach to analysing the adaptive capacity of governance regimes by focusing on change and learning. This approach examines the structural characteristics of the governance regimes associated with MarinePlan’s eight Planning Sites, as well as assessing how stakeholders participate in and contribute to regimes, the nature of policy and management processes, and the factors that enable (or prevent) change to occur in regimes.

1.1 Project outline

The diversity of terrestrial and marine life is dramatically affected by human interventions including climate change. A compelling growing evidence shows that biodiversity is the basis for ecosystem functions and services and consequently for human benefits depending on those. Thus, the importance of ecosystem biodiversity cannot be underestimated calling for an effective management of marine activities and a sustainable use of marine and coastal resources. MSP is the main governance process that ideally balances economic, ecological and socio-cultural goals through the regulation of human uses at sea. With the global and regional conservation and green energy targets ahead, there is an urgent need to define pathways for a better alignment of MSP and strategic conservation planning, hence the operationalisation of an ecosystem approach to MSP. The European Union (EU)-funded project MarinePlan supports the implementation of ecosystem-based MSP through the development of a decision support system. It will offer guidance for an improved alignment of MSP, spatial conservation and restoration measures during the challenging times of ever-increasing pressures on marine ecosystems.

MarinePlan’s main goal will be achieved through four specific objectives for the European seas:

- #1** Co-develop with stakeholders the conceptual elements of the DSS (guidelines and tools) and derive best practice guidance for EB-MSP implementation.

#2 Develop quantitative metrics to operationalise Ecologically or Biologically Significant marine Area (EBSA) criteria and their application at various spatio-temporal scales.

#3 Implement and apply the DSS based on objectives #1 and #2, its guidelines, metrics, and tools at Planning Sites representing the diversity of European marine areas.

#4 Provide recommendations and improvements concerning the shortcomings, impediments to, and opportunities of prevailing governance processes to enhance the implementation of EB-MSP.

MarinePlan develops and applies the EB-MSP DSS within seven Work Packages and eight European Planning Sites. The Planning Sites range from coastal ecosystems to open ocean and the deep sea and from local to transboundary scales. Applying and validating the DSS incorporates realistic planning scenarios, key action points to achieve the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and policy recommendations on how to enhance EB-MSP implementation in European Seas. MarinePlan will communicate results to decision-makers at horizontal (between sectors) and vertical (from local to European) levels and enable the transfer of knowledge to areas in differing socio-ecological settings. The improved natural and social science base will ensure effective policymaking to support a greater coherence in implementing environmental policies as well as to enable streamlined planning for marine industries.

1.2 Aim of Deliverable

The task that informs D4.2, Task 4.2, involved an examination of how the governance regimes of MarinePlan's eight Planning Sites use diverse knowledge on conservation measures and MSP processes. This involved exploring stakeholders' perceptions of existing governance regimes, their opinions of what change is required to governance processes, examples of how change is advocated for, and a demonstration of how change has occurred. By assessing these factors, it becomes possible to understand the current adaptive capacity of each region's governance systems. The aim of the Deliverable is to demonstrate these assessments – by constructing and presenting an 'adaptive capacity review' for each Planning Site – and to provide a critical discussion of what these findings reveal about the current direction of travel for marine governance across Europe. This is supported by the identification of key barriers and enablers of adaptive governance, which are presented as learning lessons for marine governance going forward.

1.3 Research objectives

To complete Task 4.2, four research objectives were set for participating Planning Sites to complete. These activities were conducted between M12 (September 2023) and M24 (September 2024). By completing these objectives, the material to inform D4.2 was collected and subsequently analysed. The objectives are as follows:

- 1.** Conduct a review of documents related to MSP and MPA processes produced by non-government actors relevant to each Planning Site;
- 2.** Carry out semi-structured interviews with a diverse range of government and non-government actors relevant to MSP and MPA processes in each Planning Site;

3. Thematically analyse the collected documents and interview transcripts, creating an ‘adaptive capacity review’ for each Planning Site;
4. Share the findings of Task 4.2 at a policy roundtable event that will discuss the transferability of the results beyond the Planning Site areas.

1.4 Contributors

Each of MarinePlan’s Planning Sites – *Azores; Bay of Biscay; Campania; Celtic Sea; Greek Aegean, Ionian Sea; Southern North Sea; Western Baltic Sea; Western Mediterranean Sea* – have contributed to D4.2. The Planning Sites are central to the MarinePlan project. They will coherently apply the developed tools to derive commonalities, success stories and impediments with regard to the co-development of feasible and realistic planning options to achieve EU Biodiversity strategy targets with the help of an ecosystem approach to EB-MSP. Table 1 (below) indicates the members of the MarinePlan project who have contributed to the development of D4.2.

Contributor name	Affiliation	Role	Planning Site
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Table 1. Names and roles of contributors to D4.2.

1.5 Structure of the report

The following section ([section 2](#)) presents an overview of the key themes that inform this report. This includes a review of seminal literature regarding the topics of adaptive governance ([section 2.1](#)), advocacy ([section 2.2](#)) and multi-level learning ([section 2.3](#)). It is explained how these themes are used to design Task 4.2 and to structure each Planning Site's 'adaptive capacity review'. [Section 3](#) explains the methodological framework that was developed to guide the research conducted to inform this report. This includes a discussion of the research design that was created, the data collection and analysis approaches that were used, and the ethical factors that were considered before initiating the research. [Section 4](#) includes the findings of the research, presenting an 'adaptive capacity review' for each Planning Site. These reviews demonstrate the existing governance problems facing each Planning Site, how stakeholders advocate for change, and to what extent subsequent learning and change have

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occurred within each region's governance regime. Following this, [Section 5](#) provides a synthesis of the findings and some final remarks. This section demonstrates some of the key barriers and enablers to adaptive capacity. [Section 6](#) concludes D4.2 by outlining the next steps that this report will inform.

2. Adaptive governance, advocacy and multi-level learning

Marine governance involves the formal and informal institutions that structure political, economic and social interaction (Elliott et al., 2023; Kelly et al., 2018; van Tatenhove, 2017). This includes laws, policies, conflict resolution, public consultations and other decision-making processes (Greenhill et al., 2020). Marine governance regimes are formally institutionalised and directly influence the agendas and contexts in which decisions are contested and access to resources is determined (Levi-Faur, 2012). It is important to note that there is a difference between governance and management. Management relates to the formal processes of decision-making, coordination and resource deployment that occur within a given institutional setting (Österblom and Folke, 2013). In management, there is direct control over resources and the behaviour of agents. Governance, on the other hand, refers to the influence or indirect control of one agent, or a group of agents, over decisions or behaviour (Tihanyi et al., 2014). Focusing on marine governance, scholars have clarified how governance considers the deliberation and determination of the goals of management, including the values, norms and principles underpinning them (Greenhill et al., 2020; Qiu and Jones, 2013; Some et al., 2015; Stelzenmüller et al., 2024). Governance regimes consist of a network of actors. This includes state actors, such as governmental entities and municipalities, as well as a multitude of stakeholders, comprising of eNGOs and communities, and marine sector representatives (van Leeuwen and van Tatenhove, 2010). Understanding the interactions, power balances and exchanges of knowledge between network actors is key to any analysis of marine governance operations (McAteer and Flannery, 2024). In this assessment of marine governance, which specifically looks into the scope of governance regimes to adapt to emerging problems and challenges, the themes of adaptive governance, advocacy, and multi-level learning are of vital importance. The following sub-sections explain these themes, clarifying how they provide a structure for analysing the adaptive capacity of each Planning Sites' respective governance regime.

2.1 Adaptive governance

The first use of the term adaptive governance is widely credited to Dietz et al. (2003). In time, it has grown in prominence as an analytical approach to understanding forms of governance that have the ability to acknowledge uncertainty and to facilitate responses to change (Armitage et al., 2009; Chaffin et al., 2014; Wyborn, 2015). Adaptive governance is framed around goals of social-ecological sustainability and policy solutions that are designed to realise a more sustainable future. These goals, and the adaptive capacity in governance to reach them, are assumed as inherently desirable (Chaffin et al., 2014). It thus refers to “*the evolution of the rules and norms that promote the satisfaction of underlying human needs and preferences given changes in understanding, objectives, and the social, economic and environmental context*” (Hatfield-Dodds et al., 2007: 4). A key concept used in adaptive governance theory is adaptive capacity. This refers to the ability of a system or individual to adjust to changing conditions or recover from the impacts of change (Quimby and Levine, 2021). Adaptive capacity is determined by the structures and processes that enable or constrain choices for action by actors, individually and collectively. It also reflects learning and an ability to experiment to foster innovative responses and solutions to system change (Österblom and Folke, 2013). Adaptive governance opens up discussions about processes and situations that allow for the reorganisation of governance in a manner flexible enough to guide marine management despite extreme uncertainty and complexity (Dutra et al., 2019; Greenhill et al., 2020; Stelzenmüller et al., 2024). While adaptive governance cannot be mandated, it can be facilitated by legal mechanisms that allow governance to respond to

dynamic social and ecological challenges over time (Cosens et al., 2017; Craig et al., 2017). Changing institutional arrangements can also provide ‘windows of opportunity’ for institutional innovation and for adaptive governance practice to emerge (Olsson et al., 2006). It is a useful concept to relate to when analysing how the governance regimes of each Planning Site are progressing and evolving. In doing so, it is possible to identify if regimes are reorganising and reflexively learning from past failures, or if they are demonstrating path-dependency in governance operations.

2.2 Advocacy

A key contributing factor to governance change is the process of advocacy (Balassiano and Chandler, 2010). Advocacy, particularly in the realm of public policy, is the practice of groups or individuals raising awareness of particular issues, communicating knowledge to provide evidence of claims, and calling for respective governance action (Cvitanovic et al., 2016). By advocating for the implementation or revision of specific policies, stakeholders and sectoral representatives can influence the political agenda and enable new management approaches to develop (Fyall, 2017). Advocacy activities range from legal challenges and political lobbying to more subtle processes of influence, such as grassroots or bottom-up mobilisation involving eNGO-led campaigning or activism (Fyall and McGuire, 2015; Ward et al., 2023). Combinations of both approaches can be used concurrently. Research has illustrated how advocacy can bridge the gap between stakeholders, sectors and decision-makers, whilst also functioning as a means of holding decision-makers accountable by urging them to address problems (Fyall and McGuire, 2015; Ward et al., 2023). Thus, assessing the role of advocacy is a vital element of understanding the adaptive capacity of marine governance regimes. In D4.2, evidence is presented on the type of change that stakeholders and sectors advocate for in each Planning Site. Information on the advocacy practices and techniques that are utilised by such actors is also presented. Findings demonstrate the degree to which advocacy is informing change and learning in the respective regions, with key enablers and barriers to successful advocacy exemplified.

2.3 Multi-level learning

This report presents adaptive capacity by assessing change and reorganisation in each Planning Sites’ respective marine governance regime. To understand change in such contexts, it is useful to consider learning as a multi-level process. Multi-level learning consists of processes of purposeful action and self-organisation and emergence within a governance network (Pahl-Wostl, 2009). The distinction between social and societal is made to emphasise the importance of learning in multi-actor settings and of structural change in the governance regime as a whole (Diduck, 2010). Learning is assumed to be an exploratory, stepwise search process where actors experiment with innovation until they meet constraints and new boundaries (Löff, 2013). Thus, learning has different levels of intensity and scope. To understand the different levels of learning, D4.2 links to the concept of triple-loop learning. Originally developed in organisational theory (see Hargrove, 2008), the concept has been applied to governance research (Johannessen et al., 2019; Medema et al., 2014). The triple-loop learning concept aims at a refinement of the influence of governing variables in terms of governing assumptions and governing values (Pahl-Wostl, 2009). Figure 1 (below) presents a visual representation of the model.

Figure 1. Multi-level learning loop model (Pahl-Wostl, 2009)

Multi-loop learning conceives learning as being progressively deeper across single-, double- and triple-loop contexts. Single-loop learning refers to an incremental improvement of action strategies without questioning the underlying assumptions of governance processes. This form of learning rests on the ability to detect and correct errors about a given set of operating mechanisms (Tagg, 2010). In a marine governance context, this could involve the implementation of new management measures to address marine litter. Double-loop learning refers to a revisiting of governance assumptions. This type of learning goes beyond simply adapting to emergent change. Rather, it involves revising systems and processes so that similar challenges are prevented from impacting a governance regime in the first place. In this scenario, governance regimes ‘learn to learn’ and become capable of reforming operating criteria and behaviour (Tosey et al., 2012; Williams and Brown, 2018). In triple-loop learning, a governance regime’s underlying values and beliefs are reconsidered. Triple-loop learning represents a deeper form of learning that questions why systems, processes and desired results exist in the first place. This form of learning requires the ability to improve the capacity of a network in single- and double-loop learning, by ‘learning about learning’ (Keijser et al., 2020). In practical terms, triple-loop learning involves pushing towards disruptive or transformational change in governance regimes. D4.2 demonstrates examples of single-, double- and triple-loop learning in each Planning Site.

3. Methodology

This section explains the methodological framework that was created to complete the research objectives associated with Task 4.2. Due to the various research objectives of the Task, a range of research methods were required to be utilised to ensure that the task was completed. These methods, as well as the larger research design that are a part of, are explained in the following sub-sections. The ethical considerations that were factored into this study, as well as information on the ethical approval that was granted to enable the operationalisation of the Task, are noted at the end of this section.

3.1 Data collection

A workbook for Task 4.2 was designed to guide Planning Sites on how to collect the relevant information for D4.2. This included information on how the Planning Sites were to identify and store documents, produced by non-government actors relevant to their region, related to MSP and MPA processes. Additionally, the workbook clarified how Planning Sites would be required to conduct semi-structured interviews with key marine stakeholders, including government and non-government actors. Inclusion criteria for the interviews focused on recruiting individuals who have a strong knowledge of the MSP and/or MPA processes in the Planning Site areas. It was recommended that between 5-10 interviews should be conducted by each Planning Site. It was advised that the recruitment of participants was done via purposive sampling, with specific individuals being targeted. This was achieved by the use of expert and snowball sampling forms of purposive sampling. Significant care was taken to ensure that the recruitment process was carried out equitably, ensuring that no potential participants were intentionally excluded. Potential interviewees were initially contacted via email and provided with a MarinePlan participant information sheet. Free and informed consent was obtained from all participants before the collection of data from interviews. To achieve this, potential participants were provided with a project information sheet and a consent form. When necessary, material was translated into local languages. The consent information outlined all aspects with regard to a participant's role in the research, how their information will be processed, who will have access to their information, and how they will appear anonymous.

The semi-structured interviews were guided by thematic questions. The created themes focused on perceptions of existing marine governance regimes, advocacy, learning, and the adaptive capacity of such regimes. The interviews also posed questions about the issues related to the legislative, economic, sectoral and administrative aspects within each respective Planning Site. By participating in the interviews, the participants provided vital information on the adaptive capacity of existing governance regimes and how they can facilitate more dynamic approaches to the management of MPAs and MSP. Generating insight into these themes is considered a critical step for MarinePlan to develop realistic and implementable policy recommendations. Moreover, this information enables the development of an adaptive capacity assessment for each Planning Site. These assessments provide important information on each region's responsiveness to change, evidence of learning and apparent capacity to tackle future challenges and threats.

3.2 Data analysis

Thematic analysis was then proposed as an analytical method to be conducted on the collected documents and interview transcripts. Thematic analysis is the most useful approach to capturing the complexities of meaning within a textual data set (Terry et al., 2017). Specifically, it can help to examine and provide meaning to the experiences, thoughts, or

behaviour, identified across a data set. To be completed successfully, it requires involvement and interpretation from the researcher. Thematic analysis is a form of examination that moves beyond counting explicit words or phrases and, instead, focuses on identifying and describing both implicit and explicit ideas within the data (Clarke et al., 2015). It was decided that a deductive thematic analysis was to be conducted of the documents and interview transcripts that were collected by Planning Sites. A deductive approach involves coming to the data with preconceived themes that were expected to be reflected in the data. Three themes were developed – perspectives of current governance regimes; the role of advocacy; reflexivity and adaptive capacity – based on theory and existing knowledge of marine governance research. The rationale for taking a deductive approach to this analysis was to ensure that there was commonality in the findings produced by each Planning Site. This helped to identify trends and similarities between the Planning Sites. Additionally, by following a deductive approach, it became possible to create adaptive capacity assessments for each region. These assessments demonstrate how MPAs and MSP processes are functioning within each Planning Site, with key challenges and opportunities highlighted.

3.3 Ethical considerations

Throughout the research, the anonymity of individuals and appropriate levels of confidentiality needed to be maintained. This was made clear on information sheets that were shared with participants, and participants were explicitly instructed that their identities would be concealed throughout the study. This resulted in interview data being un-attributable to participants. This process, which is explained in the consent forms and information sheets that were shared with interviewees, was made clear before the interviews commenced. To ensure the safe storage of data, collected documents and interview transcripts have been held securely on MarinePlan's SharePoint. Access to the SharePoint is restricted through password protection. Hard copies of signed consent forms have been securely stored in locked filing cabinets and are carefully protected at all times. At no point will any other individual or group who is not a co-investigator have access to the information of research participants. If a participant, for whatever reason, desired to end their participation and to have their contribution retracted, it was made clear to them that they have a window of 6-weeks after their interview to overturn their consent form. In such a scenario, none of their information would be attached to the findings of this report. The MarinePlan ethics document (Deliverable 4.4) was designed following the granting of ethical approval by Queen's University Belfast's Energy and Physical Sciences (EPS) Faculty Research Ethics Committee in December 2022, in accordance with the Proportionate Review process.

4. Findings

This section presents each Planning Site's 'adaptive capacity review'. These overviews report on the key governance problems identified in each regime, what (and how) change is advocated for by stakeholders, and to what extent change has occurred. To demonstrate how change reflects the adaptive capacity of each governance regime, examples of single-, double- and triple-loop learning are presented. Identified opportunities and barriers to adaptive marine management are also illustrated. A more detailed explanation of each sub-heading is provided below.

Overview of existing governance regime

This sub-section explains the current progress of each Planning Site in relation to MSP and MPAs. This includes an overview of the institutional and organisational context of each Planning Site, explaining the reality of how these processes are governed in each region. Examples are provided of what each regime's key objectives are and information is presented regarding the networks and structures that policy-makers participate in to achieve their policy goals.

Identified governance problems

This sub-section demonstrates the emergent challenges that are hindering MSP and MPA processes. This involves the key problems, as identified by interviewees, that are disrupting progress in each governance regime. These include challenges, such as limited coherence across government departments, tokenistic participation processes, power imbalances amongst marine sectors, and a lack of transparency in policy design. By identifying these governance problems, it then becomes possible to explore how they are (or are not) being addressed. Such information is vital in determining the adaptive capacity of governance regimes.

How stakeholders advocate for change

This sub-section demonstrates the different techniques and approaches that are used by stakeholders – from eNGO actors to representatives of marine sectors – when calling for change to governance regimes. This includes information on how proposed alterations to MSP and MPA processes are advocated for. Examples include campaigning and activist action, initiating legal proceedings, knowledge sharing, and developing collaborative partnerships and networks. These activities seek to instigate governance change to ensure that issues, such as fishing quotas, zoning, pollution, dumping of contaminants and the impacts of climate change, can be alternatively managed.

Adaptive capacity of governance

In this report, adaptive capacity is framed as the ability of a governance regime to adjust challenges, respond to consequences and take advantage of opportunities. This sub-section presents an overview of the extent to which each Planning Sites' governance regime is demonstrating adaptive capacity. Examples of change to governance frameworks, processes

and approaches are listed, while the multi-level 'learning loop' model is used to illustrate the extent of such change.

Single-loop learning

Single-loop learning refers to a refinement of actions to improve performance without changing guiding assumptions and calling into question established routines. This sub-section presents examples of incremental changes in governance practice and action aimed at improving the achievement of goals. In some instances, this involves policy and management change, whilst in others it includes a first improvement of the capacity to implement collective decisions.

Double-loop learning

Double-loop learning refers to a change in the frame of reference and the calling into question of guiding assumptions. In the sub-section, examples are presented that illustrate how regimes have reflected on goals and problem framing and altered the assumptions of how goals can be achieved accordingly. Experimentations with innovative approaches, technologies and new kinds of measures are illustrated across the regimes.

Triple-loop learning

Triple-loop learning refers to a transformation of the structural context and factors that determine governance operations. In this sub-section, indications of regime transformation are noted, including changes in regulatory frameworks and the implementation of co-management approaches. As the findings of each Planning Site indicate, this type of change is largely uncommon. However, in several Planning Sites, the prospect of transformation has become more possible due to recent advancements brought on by single- and double-loop learning.

Challenges to change

Whilst there are demonstrations of learning advancements across the Planning Site regimes, it is clear that many barriers to change remain. These are important to consider, as they will significantly influence each regime's capacity to evolve sustainably and equitably. This sub-section lists some of the key challenges that are identified by stakeholders, with several examples linked to a lack of political will, resource limitations and reinforced power imbalances.

4.1 Azores

OVERVIEW OF EXISTING GOVERNANCE REGIME

Operating autonomously from the central government, MSP coordination lies within the regional government of the Azores according to the provisions of the existing legal framework. The Situation Plan for the maritime zones surrounding the Azores archipelago – known as PSOEMA – is a fundamental instrument for promoting sustainable development at the regional level. It identifies the different uses and activities of the maritime space of the Azores, while also aiming to promote compatibilities and synergies among uses. In July 2022, the Portuguese constitutional court mandated the central government with the exclusive responsibility for the implementation of EU maritime Directives, bypassing regional authorities' influence over the matter. Whilst regional government in the Azores maintains authority over the design and implementation of MSP, this illustrated the capacity of the national government to overpower regional management. The Azores MSP plan received a non-binding favourable opinion from the consultative committee in July 2023 and is in the process of undergoing public consultation. At the same time, the regional government of the Azores signed a memorandum of understanding over the 'Blue Azores' Program. The program is designed to promote the conservation and sustainable use of marine resources by declaring 30% of the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) of the Azores as MPAs (of which 15% should be strictly protected). As of yet, the Blue Azores process has not been officially integrated into the MSP process. Due to the diversity of ocean stakeholders and the limited availability of scientific data, the process for the revision of the MPA network was conducted on the offshore network only (areas beyond 6 nm from the coastline). This will complement the existing MPA network, with eleven MPAs included in the Azores Marine Park in 2011, while three further areas were included in 2016. The existing MPA network also includes National Island Park, OSPAR, Natura 2000 and Biosphere Reserve areas.

IDENTIFIED GOVERNANCE PROBLEMS

- **National-regional relationship** – There is political complexity in the relationship between the Portuguese government and the regional government of the Azores. Ineffective integration between national and regional levels is hindering the coherence and connectivity of MSP functioning;
- **Integration between MSP and MPAs** – MPAs management has not been formally incorporated into the MSP process, resulting in uncertainty about how the processes can successfully integrate and complement each other;
- **Knowledge gaps** – Although substantial improvements in large-scale scientific data availability on specific ecosystem components have been made over the last decade, some knowledge gaps still hamper the implementation of specific MSP components;
- **Stakeholder fatigue** – Multiple ongoing projects and public consultation processes are operating across the Azores archipelago, leading to stakeholder fatigue and burnout. Most stakeholders also feel that despite such consultation processes, they are not heard and have little impact.

HOW STAKEHOLDERS ADVOCATE FOR CHANGE

- **Formal connections with government** – The development of partnerships between stakeholders and government has supported greater communication, knowledge dissemination, and power sharing. This includes the Blue Azores

project, which has been established between the regional government of the Azores, eNGOs (the Oceano Azul Foundation, the Waitt Institute) and academia (University of the Azores);

- **Fisheries associations** – To promote consistent and determined political action, an informal network of fisheries actors has been established. The network helps fishers to advocate for greater support for training and capability building, as well as promoting the greater co-production and transfer of fisheries knowledge between fishers and regional administration, economic and social agents;
- **Advisory groups** – Participation in EU advisory groups has promoted collaborative work among some stakeholders. In such settings, informal meetings and exchanges have enhanced trust between actors;
- **eNGO coalitions** – Groups of marine-focused eNGOs have developed coalitions to strengthen their collective power and join their effort to overcome limited resources. This includes the Sea Observatory of the Azores (OMA), a technical, scientific and cultural non-profit association. Its objectives are the dissemination of scientific and technological culture, as well as the promotion of activities of interpretation and environmental education.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY OF GOVERNANCE

In the Azores, several innovative solutions have been operationalised to correct for previous failings and to advance work on time-pressured objectives. For instance, a strategic approach to the identification of areas of ecological relevance, such as those that fit the criteria for identifying Ecologically or Biologically significant Marine Areas (EBSAs), has been developed. A memorandum of understanding over the Blue Azores program has been signed to finalise the identification of the relevant deep-sea areas by the end of 2024. Further progress involved devising a partnership with the Azores Deep Sea Research Group to develop a systematic conservation planning approach for the region. Preliminary results revealed knowledge gaps and mapped out pathways of action to address these. Other innovative changes include the development of the Azor drift-cam, a cost-effective video platform designed to conduct rapid appraisals of deep-sea benthic habitats down to 1,000 m depth. By advancing partnerships with international scientific organisations and trialling new technology, greater arrays of information regarding the composition and spatial distribution of benthic communities in the Azores have significantly enhanced over the last four years. These examples, as well as other instances of learning, are listed below.

SINGLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Local fisheries regulation** – New approaches to enhance fishing sustainability have been designed, particularly in the context of small-scale fisheries. Various local regulations that mitigate the impacts of targeting functionally important species have been implemented. These regulations have played a pivotal role in preserving ecological functions within the ecosystem, as well as in managing the removal of high biomass of key important species from the ecosystem;
- **Plastic neutrality fishery** – In 2022, the Azores pole-and-line fishery became the world's first plastic-neutral fishery. A model for ghost gear retrieval was developed, with the fleet removing more plastic fishing gear from the ocean, by weight, than it lost on an annual basis. Due to this success, funding has been sourced to widen the program;

- **Establishment of policy working groups** – Seven thematic working groups have been developed by the government to support the contribution of stakeholders to policymaking. These working groups – which focus on the themes of ‘fisheries and aquaculture’, ‘marine mineral resources and energy’, ‘conservation’, ‘research and technology’, ‘tourism’, ‘ports’, and ‘safety’ – have been designed to address stakeholder fatigue and power imbalances across marine sectors.

DOUBLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Implementation of new technologies** – The development of the Azor drift-cam demonstrates a shift in the willingness of the Azores’ regional government to trial alternative technology. Rather than replacing more sophisticated underwater examination tools, the Azor drift-cam provides the means to perform quick assessments simply and affordably. This is helping to redesign how the governance regime can efficiently respond to pressing data gaps, identify emerging threats and propose respective action. On a wider scale, it is also opening the door to new technology being incorporated into the governance regime;
- **Formal collaborative partnerships** – The development of partnerships between regional government, eNGOs and research institutes – such as the Blue Azores program – is an example of the government applying new ideas of how to increase co-creation. A formalised arena for co-creation should, in the long term, influence the continued interplay between marine actors for progress in sustainable and equitable marine management practice. However, it is important to note that these partnerships require continued development and maintenance. Some stakeholders perceive that the partnerships have, as of yet, failed to instil a culture of collaboration or mutual understanding within the network.

TRIPLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Co-managed MPAs** – There has been a shift toward bottom-up MPA development in the Azores. Two MPAs in the region, in Ribeira Quente and Corvo, were largely proposed and informed by local stakeholders and sectoral representatives. In conversations with governance actors, it was also revealed that lessons have been taken from the experience of a bottom-up MPA in the south of Portugal where a co-management approach has been established. Should the movement toward co-management in the design, implementation and management of MPAs in the Azores be furthered, it would demonstrate a transformation of how marine spaces are managed in the region.

CHALLENGES TO CHANGE

- **Lack of political will** – Examples of successful change in the Azores governance regime have been dependent on the government’s drive to restructure governance processes. However, there remains a lack of commitment to fully address some issues, including, the integration of MSP and MPA processes, and formally implementing MPA co-management. Without the government’s political commitment to affect action, the capacity of

D4.2 REPORT ON THE BARRIERS TO ADOPTING NOVEL AND DYNAMIC APPROACHES TO MPA DESIGNATION AND IMPLEMENTATION

novel management ideas to be implemented is likely to be significantly lower. Additionally, the government's lack of commitment to establishing a long-term marine management strategy has created uncertainty amongst stakeholders and sectors;

- **Power imbalances** – Whilst actions have been undertaken to address power imbalances between marine sectors, including the development of policy working groups, issues remain. This is leading to a lack of trust in the MSP system, in addition to mistrust between stakeholders, due to the instances of preferential focus on marine industries and developers;
- **National-regional relationship** – There remain ongoing disputes between the national and regional governments regarding who should develop, approve and adopt MSP and MPA policies in the Azores. Unless work is done to enhance integration between national and regional levels, the lack of coherence and connectivity between MSP and MPA processes will continue to broaden.

4.2 Bay of Biscay

OVERVIEW OF EXISTING GOVERNANCE REGIME

The Bay of Biscay (BoB) is a transboundary Planning Site, bordering both Spain and France. In 2023, Spain adopted its maritime spatial plan, the Planes de Ordenación del Espacio Marítimo (POEM) (Royal Decree 150/2023). POEM establishes plans for each of the five Spanish marine subdivisions, including the 'North Atlantic', which covers part of the BoB. For this subdivision, a transboundary consultation process was launched to gain the input of French marine stakeholders. Coordinated by the European Commission, a Marine Spatial Experts Group was established to fulfil this objective. In France, four maritime spatial plans, the Documents Stratégiques de Façade, were adopted between April and May 2022. A public consultation was conducted regarding the integration of new offshore renewable and biodiversity protection areas into the maritime spatial plans. Consultation relating to the revision of the plans is currently ongoing. Additionally, both Spain and France participate in the MSP Global initiative and are members of the Atlantic Action Plan. Regarding MPAs, special protection areas located in the BoB Planning Site area, such as those for seabirds and habitats in the Natura 2000 Network, were integrated into the Spanish MPAs network in 2015. In the context of the EBSA declaration, initial plans to develop working groups were abandoned due to other agenda priorities. Whilst marine governance in Spain and France has focused on addressing similar concerns, both countries, at times, have followed different methods. This has created significant problems, leading to a pressing need to enhance integration between process leaders and regional authorities.

IDENTIFIED GOVERNANCE PROBLEMS

- **Cross-border cooperation** – There remains limited transboundary cooperation when identifying priorities and developing specific objectives for the BoB region. Additionally, there has been a lack of cross-border consultation of these objectives to regional stakeholders or definition of mutual environmental issues within the region;
- **Management measures** – There is a significant difference between the program of governance measures (for instance, fisheries, pollution or biodiversity measures) outlined in France and Spain, as well as a lack of information about how such measures will contribute to achieving sustainability in the region. To monitor the applicability and effectiveness of management measures, it is vital to develop clear, quantitative objectives. As of yet, this is not possible in the BoB region;
- **Emergence of offshore energy sector** – New offshore projects are expected in the BoB, with policy documents in both countries outlining renewable energy targets (30% of total energy consumption by 2030). However, each country has an independent 'energy road map' that fails to identify common objectives or trade-offs between the nations.

HOW STAKEHOLDERS ADVOCATE FOR CHANGE

- **Collaboration between eNGOs and marine sectors** – eNGOs have developed alliances with marine sectors in an attempt to establish common long-term objectives that can be collectively advocated for. This includes international eNGOs, such as the World Wildlife Foundation (WWF), who have developed partnerships with multiple sectors in Spain, including fisheries,

tourism and aquaculture. Specifically with the fisheries sector, work has been done to collaboratively develop position reports that propose alternative approaches to MPA design and implementation, as well as provide assistance for fisheries when responding to consultation;

- **eNGOS taking legal action against the government** – In 2020, French eNGOs filed a court case against the government’s inaction to protect dolphins in the BoB. Although scientists repeatedly called for the closure of the responsible fisheries during these peak seasons, the French government refused to act on these calls. The [French High Court of State](#) recognised the inefficiency of current management and acknowledged that fisheries closures are necessary to preserve the dolphins’ population. This judgment from the High Court of State represents a historic victory for eNGOs.
- **The MPA database** – A [database](#), created by the Marine protected areas in the Atlantic arc (MAIA) INTERREG project, has been utilised as a key resource for eNGOs when advocating for the coherent management of MPAs in the BoB. The database, which contains official and updated information on international and national MPAs across Europe, represents an evidence base that has supported eNGOs’ calls for management action.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY OF GOVERNANCE

Recent developments have indicated that the transboundary BoB Planning Site is devising new approaches to address governance challenges. Many of the changes have been informed by reflecting on previous governance failures and using collaboration to identify alternative pathways forward. Some of the change can be framed as short-term measures – such as implementing fishing bans and establishing transboundary working groups – whilst others are more ambitious, long-term attempts to redesign policy, implement new technologies and transform the management of MPAs. The specific examples listed below demonstrate how successful change to a governance regime is dependent on learning and collaboration across all network actors. Not solely government, but all participating stakeholders and sectors. For instance, the work of the French Centre for Studies and Expertise on Risks, the Environment, Mobility and Urban Planning (CEREMA) to develop methodologies, tools and guidelines to support more adaptive MSP and MPA processes has been dependent on collaboration with multiple actors. [CEREMA has co-developed tools](#), such as geo-data portals, shoreline monitoring technologies and guidelines for co-managing maritime activities, with government agencies, regional authorities, research organisations, and stakeholders.

SINGLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Short-term fishing bans** – In January 2024, France introduced a one-month ban on almost all commercial fishing in the BoB to protect dolphins against the risk of regional extinction. Advocated for by three eNGOs, the Council of State, the highest jurisdiction in France, ordered the government to close certain fishing areas within six months. The ban addressed a key conservation issue in the short-term, yet failed to implement a long-term approach and frustrated the fishing sector by failing to conduct a consultation before applying the ban;
- **Establishment of transboundary working groups** – Working groups have been developed to support the creation of common platforms to share ideas and concerns from both countries’ authorities and stakeholders. Learning has been taken from successful examples of cross-border MSP cooperation that have been assessed – including HELCOM and OSPAR –

which recommend transnational policy measures. Transboundary consultation processes were launched to obtain the inputs from respective MSP documents, with a specific meeting in 2021 for that purpose. However, working groups in the BoB remain at an early stage and will require support to be successful.

DOUBLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Adaption plans** – Spain has published a [Climate Change Adaptation Plan](#), which constitutes the basic planning instrument to promote coordinated and coherent action against the effects of climate change on marine environments. In France, adaptive management measures aimed at mitigating the effects of climate change on aquatic habitats have been implemented as a result of public consultations and European funding being sourced. At the same time, applied research programs are being developed to set up predictive life cycle models;
- **Technological tools for collaboration and coordination in MSP** – [CEREMA](#) supports capacity building, training programs and research projects related to French MSP and MPA processes. It works closely with government agencies, research organisations, and stakeholders to foster collaboration. The centre develops tools, such as spatial planning software, decision-support systems, and guidelines for assessing environmental impacts. These technologies are changing how the governance system facilitates collaboration. They are also informing the development of strategic, medium- to long-term plans of action for MSP and MPA management;
- **Incentivising alternative fishing techniques** – A lack of consideration of fishers' needs and voice, as in the case of short-term fishing bans, can reinforce conflict. To counter this, French governance leaders have created economic incentives to encourage the experimentation of gentler fishing methods that have a lower impact on ecosystems. New approaches have also been developed to support greater knowledge share and communication between government and fishers;
- **Marine Natural Parks** – In France, several Marine Natural Parks have introduced new forums for knowledge sharing and communication between stakeholders, sectoral representatives and local government. In the regions where these parks are located, no such platform for direct engagement previously existed. The forums have helped to build trust between actors. This is deemed as a necessary first step in the process of implementing co-management structures in some of the parks;
- **Long-term and flexible objectives** – Spain ensures the involvement of stakeholders through the development of long-term and flexible sector objectives. Rather than designing reactionary measures that apply to short periods, a shift to long-term planning has been demonstrated. This is providing greater clarity and structure for marine sectors and stakeholders. Importantly, there is scope for evaluation and revision within such objectives.

TRIPLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Co-operative MPAs** – Whilst not in the BoB, the Cote Bleue Marine Park in France represents a bottom-up initiative based on experimental co-

operation between local public authorities and professional small-scale fisheries. Interviewees suggested that similar approaches will be followed in other MPAs, specifically those in the French region of the BoB, in the coming years. The Cote Bleue Marine Park initiative has transformed how fishing activity, marine environment protection, experimental scientific research and public awareness are operated in the region. The originality of this approach relates to the use of no-takes reserves and artificial reefs (both for production purposes and protection against illegal trawling) as complementary tools for the conservation of exploited resources and sensitive habitats. Should the movement toward cooperative MPAs in France be furthered into the BoB, it would demonstrate a transformation of how marine spaces are managed in the region.

CHALLENGES TO CHANGE

- **Cross-border cooperation** – There remains a lack of integration between France and Spain, particularly in regard to devising collaborative governance approaches. For successful change to occur in the region, much greater levels of cooperation will be required;
- **Impaired interaction between stakeholders and policymakers** – The knowledge co-creation process is hindered by tensions between the interests of stakeholders, the climate of mistrust, dense media coverage and power asymmetries between actors. In France, specifically, unless the government's engagement with the fisheries sector is transformed, opportunities for collaboration, knowledge sharing and buy-in will be missed.

4.3 Campania

OVERVIEW OF EXISTING GOVERNANCE REGIME

In the Mediterranean Sea, the Campania region (a 450 km coastline along the South West of Italy) hosts high biodiversity and multiple marine uses. Significant complexity is noted regarding the legislative landscape in the region, with an array of policies, laws and agreements at the regional, national and international levels in place. The administrative context concerning the management of Italian waters is similarly complex, with eight different government ministries holding responsibilities. The national policy goal for the protection of marine biodiversity is defined within the National Strategy for Biodiversity 2030, which is advanced as a process to create a coherent network of MPAs. However, regional administrations can implement additional local policies for specific sectors – such as aquaculture development, maritime domain planning, and Natura 2000 sites planning – creating institutional ambiguity and limited integration between national and regional marine governance structures. Whilst a national MSP process has been initiated, with an ‘Operational guidelines for the preparation of MSP in Italian waters’ report published in January 2020, MSP has yet to be formally endorsed by the Italian government. When adopted and implemented, MSP will provide guidelines for regional planners regarding their respective responsibilities in both MSP and MPA procedures. It will also clarify how the significant data gaps that face the Campania region will be addressed. This is important as it has been stated that the current challenges relating to data access and communication may prevent the establishment of an efficient and adaptive MSP process in the region. Regarding the design and implementation of MPAs in Italy, local municipalities (“comuni costieri”) play a key role as promoters of their legal implementations. In addition to the four Marine Protected Areas (“Regno di Nettuno”, “Punta Campanella”, “Santa Maria di Castellabate”, and “Costa degli Infreschi e della Masseta”) and the only two nationally recognized Submerged Parks (“Baia” and “Gaiola”), the maritime zone of the Campania region encompasses several other areas with distinct levels of environmental protection. These include various Natura 2000 sites, which have been identified, designated, and implemented by the local environmental department. Moreover, there are two Biological Protection Zones: the “Area Penisola Sorrentina” and the “Banco di Santa Croce”.

IDENTIFIED GOVERNANCE PROBLEMS

- **Competition for space** – Already a region with high levels of cumulative pressures, conflicts among competing users are expected to increase with the growing use of maritime space. This has been identified by multiple stakeholders and sectors in public consultation processes as a concern, although it remains unclear how an adaptive process will be implemented to counter this threat;
- **Ecological connectivity among MPAs** – There is a need to develop connectivity within the Campania MPA network, principally through the identification and protection of ecological corridors. As of yet, this has not been achieved;
- **Lack of consultation activity** – Public consultation, particularly at the national level, has been identified as another important weakness of the current governance system. For instance, it is not an obligation for formal stakeholder consultations to be carried out for MPAs, as there is no mandatory requirement in this regard. It is the responsibility of MPA directors to promote stakeholder engagement through formal and informal processes;
- **MPA monitoring** – It is the responsibility of MPA directors to monitor the conservation status of habitats and species. However, it is an activity that is not carried out systematically. There is a lack of funding and dedicated personnel with specific skills to assist monitoring efforts. Currently, monitoring is largely dependent on the attainment of external funding and the involvement of research institutions.

HOW STAKEHOLDERS ADVOCATE FOR CHANGE

- **Formal and informal networks** – There are several networks promoting dialogue and cooperation in the Campania region. This includes the Union for the Mediterranean and the WestMED Initiative (which also contributes to the Western Mediterranean Sea (WMS) region). These networks include a multitude of stakeholders, ranging from eNGOs and environmental charities to the fishing, energy, transport and tourism sectors. The WestMED initiative has developed an Italian ‘hub’, which co-organises events to help lead discussions on different maritime topics. It also supports project development, helps in drafting tender applications and advises on the most applicable funding opportunities;
- **Campaigning** – A large amount of advocacy in Campania is conducted through campaigns and initiatives developed by eNGOs and environmental charities. These include the organisation Blue Marine, which has launched an initiative to connect MPAs across the Campania region (and beyond). The project will link seven sea-conservation projects at MPAs and support Italy’s MPAs to bring more effective protection to their waters. Additionally, the Clean Sea LIFE initiative was an awareness-raising project that reduced marine litter along Italian coasts. The team involved 170,000 citizens and fishers who removed 112 tonnes of waste from the Mediterranean. The campaign reached around 34 million people on social media and national television. Their work inspired new Italian legislation to reduce and prevent marine litter.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY OF GOVERNANCE

In Campania, there is growing evidence of new approaches being designed and implemented to address the multiple governance challenges that the region faces. Whilst much more effort is required to continue this progression, current work provides hope that the region can efficiently develop more sustainable and adaptive governance practices. Many of the changes represent single-loop learning, including the implementation of new fisheries measures that aim to reduce the environmental impact of activities, as well as the establishment of new working groups to improve consultation and evidence of evaluations informing policy revisions. There is also evidence of campaigning directly informing management change, with the Clean Sea LIFE initiative leading to new legislation for marine litter. Other instances of learning in the region relate to changes to wider governance processes, such as the creation of an MPAs manager network that aims to support enhanced communication and knowledge sharing. The specific examples listed below demonstrate how successful change to a governance regime is dependent on learning and collaboration across all network actors. Not solely government, but all participating stakeholders and sectors.

SINGLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **New fisheries measures** – A better conservation status of the marine environment has been achieved through the implementation of multi-annual management plans and the creation of connected management objectives that are designed to minimise the environmental impacts of fishing activities;
- **Working groups** – National sectoral working groups have been organised in recent years in an attempt to respond to low levels of communication and

integration across sectors, poor participation in consultation processes, and previous failures to find common understanding amongst stakeholders. These working groups have also led to the development of specific guidelines for marine activities, particularly in the realm of fisheries and aquaculture;

- **Marine litter legislation** – The Clean Sea LIFE project contributed to national and EU policy and legislation. The project campaign, promoted by associated beneficiaries in collaboration with other eNGOs, led to a national law banning micro-beads in cosmetics in early 2020. The project inspired a draft law to facilitate ‘Fishing For Litter’ activities, and six local regulations banning balloon releases. Moreover, project staff assisted authorities in applying EU laws, for example, prosecuting a marine litter spill event;
- **MSP monitoring and evaluation** – The fundamental purpose of the MSP monitoring program is to allow the evaluation of the effectiveness of the drafted MSP plan and the progress of the plan’s actions. Recent reviews informed the drafting of a National Environmental Restoration Plan, which identified the priority areas to be restored in the Campania region and the restoration measures that should be adopted.

DOUBLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Network of MPA managers** – MedPAN is a network of MPA managers in the Mediterranean which promotes guidelines, recommendations, good practices, and practical tools to support the development of management plans. There is a network at the Mediterranean level for the Specially Protected Areas of Mediterranean Importance (SPAMIs) which represents MPAs declared in the frame of the Barcelona Convention. The network is financed by the Italian Ministry of the Environment, in which SPAMI managers exchange good practices and hold in-person meetings to co-develop approaches to resolving common issues;
- **SMART objectives for MPAs** – The Blue Marine initiative, in collaboration with the Italian government, is in the process of strengthening the management plans of MPAs by co-designing new conservation strategies that focus on Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Time-bound (SMART) objectives. This work is vital to revising the limitations of current strategies, as well as initiating a long-term framework for the management of MPAs.

TRIPLE-LOOP LEARNING

- There is no clear evidence of triple-loop learning occurring, or examples that suggest it is feasible in the near future. However, with increasing collaboration beginning to emerge – with the MPA manager network representing a key example of this – added to policy approaches being opened to revision, the Campania region is much better placed to facilitate wider governance transformation.

CHALLENGES TO CHANGE

- **Delay in MSP implementation** – The continued delay of the implementation of a national MSP for Italy is exacerbating current governance challenges. There remains a need to address the noted legislative and administrative complexity in Campania, as well as uncertainty regarding the integration of MSP and MPA processes. However, until MSP is formally adopted and in place, these challenges remain unsolved;

D4.2 REPORT ON THE BARRIERS TO ADOPTING NOVEL AND DYNAMIC APPROACHES TO MPA DESIGNATION AND IMPLEMENTATION

- **Lack of stability in MPA management** – In the management of MPAs, some significant managerial and political problems have arisen. Such problems are linked, in particular, to the lack of personnel with stable employment positions who can support directors in the management of MPAs. MPA directors are the only figures with a guaranteed salary, as additional personnel are paid by projects. Accordingly, MPA directors are commonly required to deal with multiple different roles, from administrative problems to technical-scientific issues. This places a heavy burden on directors and highlights the need for creating resourcing to support a more stable and efficient MPA management process;
- **Political will** – The effective development of adaptive marine governance in Italian waters is dependent on the political will to adopt and develop long-term, comprehensive policy. Such policy must address all implementation needs and strategically outline how to review and revise MSP and MPA objectives. Italy is lagging behind on this issue and, consequently, this is playing a significant role in the challenges faced in the Campania region.

4.4 Celtic Sea

OVERVIEW OF EXISTING GOVERNANCE REGIME

In 2021, Ireland established and approved a national MSP, known as the National Marine Planning Framework (NMPF), in accordance with the EU Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (Directive 2014/89/EU). It is complemented by The Maritime Area Planning (MAP) Act of 2021, designed to regulate activities and developments in the maritime area. Presently, the only designated marine protected sites in Ireland are declared under the EU Birds (Council 79/409/EEC) and Habitats (Council Directive 92/43/EEC) Directives, labelled as SPAs and Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) respectively. These SPAs and SACs cover approximately 9.4% of Ireland's Exclusive Economic Zone, with less than 1% occurring in the Planning Site. In December 2022, the General Scheme of the Bill for MPAs was approved by the Irish government. However, the proposed legislation has yet to progress into law. This is recognised as a key barrier to advancing marine protection in the region. It is also disrupting engagement and communication between sectors and government, with trust levels declining in the government's capacity to sustainably manage the marine environment. Most international and EU policies pertaining to marine management have been integrated into national law. Despite this, Ireland has yet to designate Other Effective Areas of Conservation Measures (OECMs) and EBSAs.

IDENTIFIED GOVERNANCE PROBLEMS

- **Silo thinking** – Limited communication between government departments responsible for marine management. While it appears that other Ministries and bodies may have overlapping jurisdictions, their cooperation is often limited to specific issues, leading to doubts about the practical implementation of this collaboration and the extent of substantial cooperation in management policies and implementation strategies;
- **Delay in finalising MPA bill** – The Government's failure to deliver the long-promised MPA bill is a major obstacle to advancing adaptive management in the Celtic Sea region. The inability to enact the Bill is, and will continue to, have serious consequences for both the State's ability to meet its offshore renewable targets and its ability to meet its international obligations to protect 30% of Ireland's seas by 2030;
- **Effectiveness of legislation** – While a large amount of legislation relating to other aspects of marine management has been adopted into national law, such as fisheries management legislation, it is unclear how effectively these policies are implemented, managed, and monitored. There is a lack of evaluation regarding current legislation and, as such, limited revisions or updates are made to such policy;
- **Competing objectives** – In addition to a lack of communication and integration across government departments, there are many competing objectives regarding the state's management of the marine environment. This is creating further uncertainty and complexity. Achieving the sustainable exploitation of the environment, whilst supporting marine conservation, remains a significant challenge. Whilst efforts are underway to develop a more holistic, Ecosystem-Based approach to marine management, this promise is yet to be realized.

HOW STAKEHOLDERS ADVOCATE FOR CHANGE

- **Transboundary collaboration** – Transboundary concerns have been taken into account in the collaboration between Ireland, Northern Ireland, and the UK during the development of the NMPF 2021. Various departments collaborate with one another and engage external stakeholders, including scientists, the fishing industry, the offshore renewable energy industry, and local communities. Formal working groups have further aided both national and transboundary partnerships. Public consultation played a crucial role in establishing the NMPF 2021;
- **eNGO coalition and campaigning for MPAs** – FAIRSEAS is a major advocacy force in Ireland. It is a coalition of Ireland's leading eNGOs and environmental networks. Fair Seas aims to build a movement of ocean stewardship across Ireland that energises and empowers people, to advocate for ambitious and robust legislation, provide impartial scientific data and research, and propose a network of effective well-managed marine protected areas. Among other stakeholders, the coalition played a pivotal role in the development and management of the (as of yet legislated) MPA bill. An advisory group, which included FAIRSEAS representatives, was convened to provide independent expert advice and recommendations on the processes required and the challenges to be addressed in expanding Ireland's MPA network. This group facilitated the sharing of knowledge and perspectives on MPAs from more than 100 key societal, community, business, and sectoral stakeholders;
- **Informal stakeholder engagement** – A further method of advocacy is through informal engagements between eNGOs, sectors and government. For instance, interactions on social media, a Green Schools poster competition supported by the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage – the department then responsible for marine planning in Ireland (this role has since changed to the Department of Environment, Climate and Communications) – and informal discussions during consultation meetings have been the effective means of communicating with policymakers. The MSP team also invited the public and stakeholders via Twitter to submit marine photographs for potential inclusion in the draft plan, which proved to be a useful means of inviting feedback and sharing perspectives.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY OF GOVERNANCE

In the Celtic Sea region, there is growing evidence of new approaches being designed and implemented to address governance challenges. This provides hope that the region can efficiently develop more sustainable and adaptive governance practices. Many of the changes represent single-loop learning, including the implementation of new marine planning measures that were largely informed by stakeholders, as well as the establishment of new working groups focused on transboundary issues and the use of innovative consultation methods. There is also evidence of campaigning directly informing management change, including the work of FAIRSEAS in informing the MPA bill. Other instances of learning in the region relate to changes to wider governance processes, such as revised participation processes and the creation of new forms of management plans. In particular, the creation of Designated Maritime Area Plans (DMAPs) – management plans for a specific area or portions of marine waters – indicates Ireland's first step into the systemic, planned development of our huge offshore wind potential. For instance, one proposed DMAP seeks to accelerate Ireland's legally binding objective of a 51% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030, by achieving 5GW of installed offshore wind capacity. The DMAPs reflect a shift in the government's program for managing future offshore renewable energy development, whereby a [plan-led approach](#) to determining potential areas for offshore wind farm developments has replaced the previous developer-led approach.

SINGLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **New planning policy informed by stakeholders** – The development of Ireland's NMPF in 2021 involved extensive public participation and stakeholder engagement. A Stakeholder Advisory Group, chaired by the minister of state, was formed to facilitate participation in the MSP process by relevant stakeholders from economic, environmental, and social sectors. Its purpose was to leverage the potential of various sectors, including representation from public, business, environmental, social, and knowledge-based domains, in guiding strategic decisions for marine spatial plans. This group encompassed representatives from eNGOs, professional bodies, and technical planning experts. The draft NMPF underwent significant revisions following extensive public consultation. This comprehensive public engagement process played a pivotal role in shaping the final NMPF.
- **Transboundary cooperation** – Transboundary cooperation is regarded as a valuable asset in policy development. Thus, transboundary concerns have been taken into account in the collaboration between Ireland, Northern Ireland, and the UK during the development of the NMPF 2021. Various departments collaborate with one another and engage external stakeholders;
- **Innovative consultation methods** – When consultation on the NMPF was halted due to the COVID-19 pandemic, online alternatives were created to ensure that participation would still occur and would have an influence on the framework without delaying it significantly. The process involved two consultative approaches, an online questionnaire and online focus groups.

DOUBLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Revised participation processes** – Learning from the successes identified during NMPF participation, more strategic and inclusive frameworks have been designed to create more effective public participation processes. This involves how the stakeholders not only share perspectives but also how they co-design policy priorities and communicate knowledge. These new approaches are particularly aimed at ensuring the growth of a wider, more informed network of stakeholders who can inform future marine management implementations;
- **DMAPs** – DMAPs are management plans for a specific area or portion of marine waters. There are several advantages of DMAPs, they provide a structured approach to managing specific areas of marine waters, sensitive habitats, biodiversity and marine ecosystems. DMAPs also establish clear rules and guidelines for activities within the designated areas, which benefits industry, investors, and other users with predictable regulations. DMAPs play a crucial role in sustainable offshore energy development. It outlines an initial 'proposed' geographical area for future offshore renewable energy development. This area will be refined through public engagement, environmental impact assessments, and expert analysis to assess its suitability. As Ireland's maritime area is seven times the size of its land mass, this is a significant milestone for offshore energy advancement. Any project seeking to develop in any of the four maritime areas will be required to obtain a Maritime Area Consent from the Maritime Area Regulatory Authority ("MARA") which will be determined in line with

the relevant provisions of the Maritime Area Planning Act 2021 ("the 2021 Act"). This system will streamline and simplify the process to enable occupation of the maritime area and planning permission in the area. Stemming from the MAP Act 2021, DMAPs are also expected to support co-location by acting as management plans for maritime areas, considering the development of multi-activity areas and accounting for potential MPAs.

TRIPLE-LOOP LEARNING

- There is no clear evidence of triple-loop learning occurring or examples that suggest it is feasible in the near future. However, with increasing collaboration beginning to emerge, added to new forms of mapping policy being designed, the Celtic Sea region is much better placed to facilitate transformation.

CHALLENGES TO CHANGE

- **Political will** – Examples of successful change in the Celtic Sea governance regime have been dependent on the government's drive to restructure governance processes. However, there remains a lack of commitment to fully address some issues, including, the much needed implementation of the MPA bill. Without the government's political commitment to initiate action, the capacity of new protection frameworks is likely to be significantly lower;
- **Lack of resources** – The insufficient resources in the designation of protected sites have posed significant challenges in implementing and monitoring these areas. The MPA Bill was designed to address this challenge, yet it has not been published, with both a lack of political will and limited resources appearing to be key challenges. Budget issues, specifically, represent a very real barrier to not only achieving the region's goals and objectives but also to supporting innovation in marine management;
- **Power imbalances** – Whilst actions have been undertaken to address power imbalances between marine sectors, including the development of policy working groups, issues remain. This is leading to a lack of trust in the Irish MSP system by some stakeholders, due to the instances of preferential focus on marine industries and developers.

4.5 Greek Aegean, Ionian Sea

OVERVIEW OF EXISTING GOVERNANCE REGIME

The Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site constitutes a national Planning Site that adheres to the overall policy framework of Greece. The fundamental legislative process for declaring protected areas in Greece includes the elaboration of a Special Environmental Study and a Management Plan for each Protected Area. The integration of the EU MSP Directive into Greek policy includes establishing a National Maritime Spatial Strategy and Maritime Spatial Frameworks. The Strategy outlines policy principles for sustainable maritime development, managing interactions between coastal and maritime areas, and coordinating policies with spatial implications. Both the development of MSP and MPA policies are led by the Ministry of the Environment and Energy in collaboration with other national authorities, with active engagement of external stakeholders. While the formulation of MPA policy is led by the Ministry of Environment and Energy, there has been a significant shift since 2020 in MPA management from local entities to a more centralized governance system under N.E.C.C.A. This change has significantly influenced how MPA policy is developed in the region. Despite the long-standing institutionalisation of the policy development process for both sectors, Greece has not fulfilled its obligations in either of them, leading to significant management challenges for the region. Additionally, Greece has yet to implement MSP. Whilst a pilot study for the first spatial plan has been conducted, MSP has not been put up for consultation. As a result of this delay, the country was referred to the European court in late 2023 for failing to deliver its spatial plans. The only existing plans are regional plans, which address specific coastal and marine areas, and sectoral plans, such as an aquaculture plan. In relation to MPAs, the Greek Prime Minister announced the creation of two additional marine parks in the Aegean and Ionian to meet the EU biodiversity targets of protecting 30% of marine waters. Special Environmental Studies, which adjust zoning and permitted activities in protected areas, are also part of this process. Such studies are the main regulatory framework for managing MPAs but have not been completed for all areas.

IDENTIFIED GOVERNANCE PROBLEMS

- **Delay of policy implementation** – A policy reformation is an emergent concern regarding MSP in Greece, as the country faces delays beyond the initial deadlines for coastal EU countries to establish MSP. Whilst an MSP strategy has been formulated, it has not yet been institutionalised. Currently, only one out of the four MSP frameworks has undergone public consultation, with the other three studies yet to begin. MPAs are considered vital for MSP, taking into account the 30% target by 2030. However, full integration of MPAs into MSP implementation remains a work in progress as the national strategy merely outlines principles and general guidelines;
- **Silo thinking** – Limited communication between government departments responsible for marine management. While it appears that other Ministries and bodies may have overlapping jurisdictions, their cooperation is often limited to specific issues, leading to doubts about the practical implementation of this collaboration and the extent of substantial co-formation in management policies and implementation of strategies;
- **Input of scientific information** – Scientific advisors of the ministry express discomfort about the low level of engagement with scientific institutions, feeling that their suggestions are not adequately considered. Interaction tends to revolve around questioning rather than fostering a constructive dialogue and making collective progress. Scientists revealed how they often feel that their knowledge and suggestions are either not accepted or disregarded altogether;

- **Policy implementation** – The Greek state has effectively incorporated most of the European regulations into its national policy. Although this is an encouraging finding, suggesting quick reflexes in policy integration, the overall analysis indicates that mere legislative compliance does not guarantee implementation. Greece often struggles to diligently incorporate the ongoing influx of European regulations, resulting in delays and the need to take more steps than manageable. The state lacks the executive capacity to turn its commitments into actionable steps. The EU Habitats Directive stands out as the most closely monitored legislative document over time. However, Greece has not yet identified any OECMs or officially ratified EBSAs.

HOW STAKEHOLDERS ADVOCATE FOR CHANGE

- **Transboundary collaboration** – Transboundary collaboration for advocacy involves sharing information, knowledge, and resources with international eNGOs, drawing from their experiences to adapt best to the national context. Collaboration with international conventions like Bern and Barcelona, plays a crucial role in advocating at the European level, sometimes involving direct actions like filing complaints with the European Union to escalate issues to the European Court of Justice;
- **eNGO coalition and campaigning for MPAs** – eNGOs often form coalitions to strengthen advocacy efforts, especially for MPAs. The coalitions embark on joint actions, such as addressing the Prime Minister on critical issues like the establishment of new marine parks, campaigning against environmentally destructive policies, and lobbying the central government. This collective approach strengthens their voice, allowing them to influence policy decisions more effectively, whether through direct communication with government officials or public campaigns like signature collections;
- **Informal stakeholder engagement** – A further method of advocacy is through informal engagements between eNGOs, sectors and government. These engagements occur through bilateral communication, such as email exchanges, results and technical reports sharing, and roundtable meetings, as well as direct political meetings at ministries and participation in legislative consultations. The effectiveness of this approach also relies on the credibility and reliability of the scientific data provided, fostering trust and influencing decision-making processes through advocacy, lobbying, and strategic recommendations.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY OF GOVERNANCE

The Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas Planning Site currently demonstrates limited levels of adaptivity, with both MSP- and MPA-related actors reporting different problems in implementing adaptive strategies. In certain MPAs, the absence of Management Plans is compensated through yearly management plans prepared by the management units. While these plans are revised yearly, adhering to the principles of adaptive management, they lack sufficient institutional support. The main challenges to formulating and implementing MPA policy within the Planning Site revolve around a lack of government willingness to integrate different forms of knowledge concerning the marine realm and the absence of a robust institutional framework. A lack of legislation regarding environmental protection is also viewed as an obstacle to developing greater adaptivity in the region, with biodiversity rarely prioritised in political agendas. In regard to MSP, there are concerns about effectively integrating the rapidly evolving global changes and the swiftly adopted regulations into national planning. This notwithstanding, there is evidence of learning across the governance regime. Many of the changes represent single-loop learning, including the updating of legislation, the development

of regional plans to accommodate for the lack of MSP, and increasing transboundary cooperation. There are also some examples of innovative solutions being implemented, including alternative approaches to protection and the redesign of some consultation initiatives.

SINGLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Updating legislation** – Efforts are underway to update policies in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, as the current Natura Network's marine areas cover approximately 18% of the country after their last revision in 2017. The country plans to establish two large marine parks, one in the Aegean Sea and one in the Ionian Sea, to meet the EU Strategy coverage targets. The Ministry of the Environment is currently implementing Special Environmental Studies to outline land use, terms, and activities within protected areas. Another ongoing program monitors species and habitats listed in the Habitats Directive Annexes. The Monitoring Program, set to conclude in 2026, will reassess the Natura 2000 network in Greece and guide its expansion. A project to map Marine Habitat Types in Natura 2000 areas lacking this information is also scheduled to start soon;
- **Regional plans** – In the absence of finalized MSP frameworks, 'Regional Spatial Plans' have been employed to offer guidelines for spatial planning in regional marine areas;
- **Research programs** – In addition to formal processes, stakeholder engagement for MSP is also facilitated through participation in EU-funded research projects. Many projects hold meetings and workshops to exchange knowledge and integrate stakeholders' opinions into planning and policy processes;
- **Transboundary cooperation** – Transboundary cooperation is regarded as a valuable asset in policy development. Legislation promotes transboundary collaborations by seeking the opinions of non-EU members in any possible way, not only through the Strategic Environmental Assessment – which is the phase in which neighbouring EU countries are asked to provide opinions on MSP – but also through forums like SPA/RAC, involving all Mediterranean countries. Whilst transboundary cooperation has been limited at times, these new approaches appear capable of rectifying this issue.

DOUBLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Policy reformation** – Greece is undergoing reforms and policy introductions, including the implementation of a National Maritime Spatial Strategy, Marine Spatial Frameworks, and Special Environmental Studies. These initiatives will lay the foundation for MSP implementation, delineate land/sea uses and management options within MPAs, and pave the way for their subsequent revision and expansion;
- **Alternative protection designation** – Greece has recently taken a significant step forward in regards to enhancing its marine protection by recognising Key Biodiversity Areas (KBAs) in its laws and policies. These areas offer an alternative protection scheme that could complement other approaches. The introduction of KBAs suggests that the governance regime is becoming increasingly capable of trialling alternative and

innovative approaches to tackle some of the long-standing issues hindering marine protection in the region;

- **Revising consultation** – At the local level, stakeholder involvement previously centred on local advisory committees (which lacked any institutional influence) or informal partnerships between management units, local authorities, eNGOs, sectoral representatives and members of the public. Following the revision of consultation activities, interactions have shown favourable outcomes, particularly in regions where management units or eNGOs have established a long-term presence and operation. Due to efforts of the management bodies to trial new approaches to consultation – including co-development initiatives, institutional working groups and more formalised partnerships – levels of cooperation between government and marine actors have significantly increased.

TRIPLE-LOOP LEARNING

- There is no clear evidence of triple-loop learning occurring or examples that suggest it is feasible in the near future. Regional plans serve as temporary fixes for the absence of proper Marine Spatial Plans, with limited consideration for marine affairs. Although regional plans are developed and occasionally revised, they do not seem to drive meaningful positive change. Transboundary collaboration is also a tricky issue for Greece, particularly due to unresolved boundary disputes with Turkey, a significant geopolitical concern that affects MPA establishment. While some transboundary collaboration is facilitated through projects and fora, this does not effectively translate into policy nor does it provide a foundation for transformative change in the region.

CHALLENGES TO CHANGE

- **Progress of MSP** – As MSP remains an ongoing process in Greece, many uncertainties regarding the wider governance of the region remain. Until MSP becomes fully implemented and operational, there is a lack of clarity on the direction of travel in the region;
- **Bottom-up approach** – In Greece, stakeholder engagement is often limited to perfunctory consultations, devoid of any active or effective participation. Deeper dialogue with citizens and local communities is often lacking, even with those directly impacted, as well as with stakeholders from sectors like tourism, energy, and fisheries. A more inclusive governance approach, where responsible bodies are willing to effectively communicate with citizens, invest effort into listening and explaining and providing time to understand changes, is not in place;
- **Political will** – Examples of successful change in the Greek Aegean, Ionian Seas governance regime have been dependent on the government's drive to restructure governance processes. However, there remains a lack of commitment to fully address some issues, including, the much needed implementation of MSP. Without the government's political commitment to initiate action, the capacity of new management frameworks to support adaptive governance in the region is likely to be significantly lower;
- **Power imbalances** – Despite the revision of some consultation processes demonstrating success, industrial sectors, such as fisheries, aquaculture and renewable energy, continue to wield greater influence over smaller stakeholders in

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some settings. This must be rectified, should sustainable and inclusive governance be facilitated in Greece;

- **Lack of evaluation** – To undertake assessment measures for MPA management, Management Plans are required. Whilst in certain MPAs, the absence of Management Plans is compensated through yearly management plans prepared by the management units, they often lack sufficient institutional support. The same goes for MSP. While the legislative framework for MSP is in place, its practical implementation is yet to be observed;
- **Employee shortfall** – Employee shortfall is a key factor undermining the adaptive capacity of government bodies. There is a lack of personnel, meaning that management bodies essentially operate reactively rather than proactively in many scenarios. This is hindering reflective actions or adaptation to policies through a systematic approach.

4.6 Southern North Sea

OVERVIEW OF EXISTING GOVERNANCE REGIME

The Southern North Sea (SNS) case study encompasses four countries: Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany and part of England. As part of the North Sea, it is an intensively used and industrialised area. All the included countries have a Maritime Spatial Plan that is implemented and legally binding. Of the four countries included in the SNS case study, two are federal states - Belgium and Germany – and two are unitary states – The Netherlands and the UK. While all four countries included in the SNS case study have an implemented MSP, some being at their second or third round, the process differs from one country to another. In Belgium, the current MSP is a 6-year plan, from 2020 until 2026, and is the country's second MSP. A strong emphasis is put on the development of marine multi-use, referring to the combination of activities at sea. In Germany, the current MSP was implemented in 2021 and is the country's second MSP. However, it is useful to note that German MSP and MPA implementations are two independent processes, undertaken by two different federal agencies. The Netherlands is currently in its third MSP, covering the period 2022-2027. The current Dutch MSP has a strong focus on offshore wind farm development, as one of the main strategies in the Netherlands to attain climate objectives for 2050 is through sustainable energy production. For the protection and conservation of the marine ecosystem, nine MPAs are defined by the Dutch MSP. In England, The Marine Management Organisation is preparing plans for 11 predefined areas. The first set of marine plans for English waters provides more detailed, area-specific guidance on marine issues. Similar to the Netherlands, strong emphasis is put on offshore wind energy production. Two types of MPAs are reported in England, namely NATURA 2000 (Birds or Habitats Directive) areas and Marine Conservation Zones (MCZs). MSP remains a tool used at a national perspective without fully considering the North Sea as one ecosystem, in need of homogeneous management.

IDENTIFIED GOVERNANCE PROBLEMS

- **Transboundary cooperation** – There remains limited transboundary cooperation when identifying priorities and developing specific objectives for the SNS region. Additionally, there has been a lack of cross-border consultation of these objectives to regional stakeholders or definition of mutual environmental issues within the region;
- **Policy complexity** – Complexity and fragmentation of legislation exist regarding the issues that MSP has to consider in the SNS region. There is no unification that encompasses the protection of marine ecosystems across the region, nor is there a general marine law that can guide transboundary cooperation. Whilst the UNCLOS is a unique law regarding marine issues, it is too general and it lacks specific guidance regarding MSP or MPAs processes across nations;
- **Stakeholder cooperation** – In the first German MSP, fisheries did not wish to be involved because they saw themselves as losers of the process, but they got more involved in the second plan although the sector is quite unhappy with the direction of modern policies. The offshore wind sector and the nature conservation sector have conflicting uses and requests when it comes to MSP in Germany, and it was one of the major discussions in the stakeholder consultation process. Because of the current energy crises, the offshore wind sector is often given priority over nature conservation and fisheries. The general public rarely gets involved in the MSP process, likely because it only concerns the EEZ which does not directly affect citizens;
- **Role of eNGOS** – In England, it is noted that some marine-focused eNGOs, when operating with formal connections to the government, are being conscripted into roles that contradict their core objectives. This includes eNGOs that have been pushed to restrict their research activities to focus solely on collecting policy-relevant knowledge,

as well as organisations that are being tasked with operating beyond their administrative capacities. These issues present a significant challenge to eNGOs, many of whom are reliant on government funding. Unless power balances can be found between the government and eNGOs, working relationships could deteriorate and greater data gaps emerge.

HOW STAKEHOLDERS ADVOCATE FOR CHANGE

- **Research institutes** – In Belgium, the public research institute ‘Royal Belgian institute of Natural Sciences’ is strongly involved in the MSP process to provide scientific advice to policymakers. In Germany, scientific advice is provided, amongst others, by the Thuenen research institute. Such institutes provide a vital channel to communicate information to governance arenas and to provide evidence to support advocacy initiatives;
- **Research projects** – There are a multitude of research projects that operate throughout the SNS region which facilitate advocacy. One example is the BLUE CONNECT project, which aims to support the effective achievement of marine conservation and restoration targets in the EU. The project has enacted a co-development approach in cooperation with site-specific stakeholders and citizens in 12 Demonstration sites across Europe. As well as offering participants a pathway to voice their opinion on marine management matters, the project is establishing co-ownership for the effective conservation management in study areas;
- **Collaboration between eNGOs and marine sectors** – eNGOs have developed alliances with marine sectors in an attempt to establish common long-term objectives that can be collectively advocated for. This includes international eNGOs, such as the WWF, who have developed partnerships with multiple sectors in the Netherlands, Germany, Belgium and the UK, including fisheries, tourism and aquaculture. Specifically with the fisheries sector of each nation, work has been done to collaboratively develop position reports that propose alternative approaches to MPA design and implementation, as well as provide assistance for fisheries when responding to consultation;
- **Committees** – All marine sectors are involved in the making of the plan, first by being represented by a governmental committee, then with exchanges with private entities, such as eNGOs (4Seas being the umbrella for Belgian eNGOs working on the Belgian part of the North Sea, also called the BPNS) and industries (Blue Cluster being the umbrella for industries working in the BPNS);
- **Advisory groups** – Participation in EU advisory groups has promoted collaborative work among some stakeholders. In such settings, informal meetings and exchanges have enhanced trust between actors.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY OF GOVERNANCE

As MSP remains a young process and policy even in Northern Europe, proper reflexive and adaptive capacity is difficult. In Germany, the second MSP was made by looking at what happened with the first one and learning from it to design the second one. In Belgium, there is a formal annual meeting with the governmental committees to assess the state of implementation of the MSP and discuss how things are going. Monitoring of activities is also still in its beginnings. In Germany, a monitoring and evaluation strategy is currently under discussion. In Belgium, monitoring of the MSP currently relies on two other policies and monitoring strategies: the MSFD and the NATURA 2000 ones, and the N2000 does not have a monitoring strategy yet so it is making use of available data from other programs (including the MSFD). Lack of space, contradictory objectives and complexity of the policy system are

cited in both Belgium and Germany as major challenges in the MSP process. Ocean multi-use might provide some solutions and is being investigated in both countries, but budgets are limited and decisions must be made that prioritize one over the other.

SINGLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Flexible evaluation periods** – In Germany, MSP is to be updated every 10 years. However, it can be updated during this period to adjust some areas allocation, such as the allocation of OWFs areas;
- **Online consultation** – As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, stakeholder participation moved into digital formats. Online meetings were held with interested parties, to go over interim results of subject areas, and share their views on future offshore wind farms locations and general preferences over space allocation;
- **Transboundary consultation** – The neighbouring countries were given an English translation of the document and were given a month of official consultation period. After taking into consideration received feedback from all parties, a final version of the MSP was designed and adopted in March 2022.

DOUBLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Revising consultation** – In Belgium, prior to public consultation, informal exchanges happen in the making of an MSP draft. Currently, the 2026-2034 planning has started, and it was launched by a kick-off event gathering all major stakeholders. Then comes a written request for stakeholders to formulate their wishes and ideas. The propositions are reviewed and the most promising ones are selected for further discussion. Then round tables are organized with relevant sectors to discuss potential use conflicts and reach acceptable compromises. After this first informal process, a pre-draft is made and taken into public consultation. Coastal communities are encouraged to hold their own event to present the draft and provide feedback;
- **Redesigning monitoring approaches** – A new monitoring program is under elaboration, the MONS (Monitoring, Research, Nature Enhancement and Species Protection Program), is meant to be an integrated assessment of the North Sea to ensure that its use remains within the ecosystem carrying capacity. Adaptive planning is well envisioned in the Dutch MSP, amendments to the adopted policy and management may be required as a result of new insights from monitoring, new (scientific) knowledge, new national and international regulations, strategies and objectives;
- **Supporting innovation** – In 2023, the Dutch government launched a maritime manufacturing industrial policy in collaboration with the maritime sector, aimed at driving the transition to cleaner energy. The effort sets the stage for a joint investment of €60 million in innovative shipbuilding over the next two years and addresses critical challenges and opportunities within the maritime sector;
- **Ocean multi-use** – Ocean multi-use might provide some solutions and is being investigated in Belgium and Germany. Ocean multi-use is an innovative approach that involves intentional joint use of resources (physical space, platforms, logistics, etc.) by two or more users, such as offshore wind and sustainable aquaculture or nature restoration. It

represents a radical change from the traditional concept of exclusive resource rights to the inclusive sharing of resources by multiple users. This holistic approach to marine resources management can help reconcile different national priorities, such as energy security, marine protection and the continuation of sustainable fishing tradition. However, in the SNS, budgets are limited and decisions must be made that prioritize one over the other.

TRIPLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Fisheries co-management** – A movement toward fisheries co-management has grown within the SNS region in recent years. Co-management refers to situations in which responsibility for resource management is shared between managing authorities and user groups. In the Netherlands, co-management strategies with producer organisations have been developed, wherein fisheries actors participate in advisory groups to co-design fishing quota allocations. Similar examples have been noted in the UK, where sectoral quota co-management programmes have been established between government and producer organisations. These indicate a willingness amongst governments to enhance co-management activities. Should this continue, it will play a key role in transforming how marine sectors engage with government, identify opportunities for collaboration and co-develop future pathways of action.

CHALLENGES TO CHANGE

- **Policy complexity** – Germany and Belgium are federal states that already deal with different levels of policy-making and the distribution of competencies that must be aligned throughout all levels. With EU competencies on top of it, with fisheries being a European competency, the complexity of the system is a barrier to dealing with users of the sea and reaching economic, environmental and sustainable objectives;
- **Lack of resources** – The insufficient resources in the designation of protected sites have posed significant challenges in implementing and monitoring these areas. Budget issues remain a very real barrier to achieving all European goals and strategies;
- **Transboundary cooperation** – Whilst the level of formal cross-border cooperation between SNS nations has increased in recent years, it remains a key challenge moving forward. There is a critical need to better identify transboundary priorities and develop specific joint objectives for the region. Additionally, there has been a lack of cross-border consultation of these objectives to regional stakeholders or definition of mutual environmental issues within the region.

4.7 Western Baltic Sea

OVERVIEW OF EXISTING GOVERNANCE REGIME

The Western Baltic Sea (WBS) is a transition area between the fully marine areas bordering the North Sea and the brackish parts of the Baltic Sea. It is a transboundary area, with Denmark and Germany surrounding the region. For Germany, the construction of new wind farms, the process of salvaging old munitions and the reinforcement of marine protection have become priorities. In Denmark, many current protected areas have a single purpose use, and while birds are protected, fishing activities continue in many of the same areas. Denmark adopted and launched its Maritime Spatial Plan in March 2021. The Danish MSP was issued as an executive order and is, therefore, legally binding. The Danish MSP is the first legally binding digital map of Denmark and the Danish waters. Before 2021, Denmark did not have a holistic spatial plan for the sea, however, a range of sectoral plans have been in use. In Germany, the current MSP was implemented in 2021 and is the country's second MSP. However, it is useful to note that German MSP and MPA implementations are two independent processes, undertaken by two different federal agencies.

IDENTIFIED GOVERNANCE PROBLEMS

- **Policy complexity** – Complexity and fragmentation of legislation exist regarding the issues that MSP has to consider. There is no process that encompasses the protection of marine ecosystems across the region, nor is there a general marine law that can guide transboundary cooperation. Whilst the UNCLOS is a unique law regarding marine issues, it is too general and it lacks specific guidance regarding MSP or MPAs processes across nations;
- **Efficiency of protected sites** – There is uncertainty regarding the efficiency of existing Natura 2000 sites and other protection areas to protect local biodiversity hotspots and the life-history connectivity of the important commercial fish species. There have been limited reviews conducted regarding this aspect, meaning that the true level of protection in the WMS region remains unclear;
- **Interference of zones** – Another governance challenge relates to the interference of offshore wind farms and gravel extraction activities with biodiversity hotspots and traditional fishing grounds. Recent years have seen a rise in the development of such activities, yet little has been done from a governance perspective to safeguard biodiversity and local fishing operations;
- **Sectoral conflict** – Whilst conflict exists between many marine sectors in the WMS region, it is particularly pronounced in the relationship between fisheries and environmentalists. Whilst the creation of MSP working groups and advisory panels has helped to enhance engagement between some sectors, many disputes remain in the relationship between the fisheries sector and eNGOs.

HOW STAKEHOLDERS ADVOCATE FOR CHANGE

- **MSP working group** – The working group on MSP consists of representatives of 12 maritime authorities in Denmark. The Danish Maritime Authority, in collaboration with this working group, is currently working towards creating a plan that takes all sectors of interest into consideration;
- **Thematic workshops** – In Germany, the MSP development process also included thematic workshops on shipping, marine conservation, fisheries, underwater cultural heritage, defence and raw materials;

- **Advisory panels** – Participation in EU advisory panels has promoted collaborative work among some stakeholders – although not between the fisheries sector and eNGOs. Advisory groups have facilitated informal meetings between some sectors, such as in workshops and policy-relevant working groups, with suggestions that the exchanges have enhanced trust between some actors;
- **eNGOS taking legal action against government** – In Germany, Environmental Action Germany (DUH) is a politically independent, non-profit organisation, entitled to bring legal action to support environmental protection. DUH has an ‘in-house’ legal team that actively responds to new laws surrounding issues, such as offshore wind development. As an example, in 2022, DUH filed legal action against an energy developer, TotalEnergies, due to an advertising statement concerning "CO₂-compensated heating oil." TotalEnergies claimed to offset the CO₂ emissions of the oil as part of its climate plan. DUH argued that this advertising claim constituted misleading commercial practices. The Düsseldorf Regional Court fully upheld DUH's lawsuit, ruling that TotalEnergies claims of climate neutrality were misleading;
- **Offshore Coalition for Energy and Nature** – The Offshore Coalition for Energy and Nature (OCEaN) provides an open forum for discussion and engagement between different European marine actors. In the coalition, existing information and experiences are collected and assessed, needs for further research are identified, and solutions on how to improve and speed up the planning deployment of offshore wind development and grid infrastructure, while preserving and restoring our European seas, are jointly designed. Recently, a separate ‘North and Baltic Seas’ working group was established within OCEaN. The Danish Society for Nature Conservation – a membership organisation that works to conserve nature and the environment in Denmark through local work, conservation, lobbying and specific projects – is a key contributor to the group.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY OF GOVERNANCE

Both the Danish and the German MSPs are subjected to re-evaluation after 5-years. In parallel, several monitoring initiatives in both countries produce data on the environmental state. In Germany, a monitoring and evaluation strategy is currently under discussion. However, monitoring and MSP are not coordinated to measure the effectiveness of the Marine Spatial Plans to date. Neither is there an unambiguous definition of effectiveness due to the multi-user nature of the sea region. This includes the lack of priorities, for example, ecological or economic targets. In addition, strong competition for space among diverse and partly conflicting stakeholder interests, contradictory objectives and complexity of the national and EU policy system are cited in both Denmark and Germany as major challenges to establishing greater adaptive capacity in the MSP process. Despite these challenges, some examples of single-loop are identified in the region. This includes the revision of some coordination activities, as well as some evidence of how consultation processes led to policy change in the region. Additionally, the creation of new data infrastructures in the region suggests that the governance regime is beginning to demonstrate greater levels of innovation.

SINGLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Revision of coordination** – With the MSP Act, the Danish government has recognised the need for greater coordination between activities conducted in the Danish marine space and between the authorities that manage and regulate these activities. These authorities have worked together through formal channels to coordinate their work and to establish new joint

initiatives. Implementation of the MSP Act will draw on and build upon the established background of this interagency collaboration;

- **Input from consultation** – Based on the results of the multi-consultation steps and the Strategic Environmental Assessment, the federal government of Denmark utilised feedback to implement change to both textual and spatial designation. A further round of consultation was also opened to ensure that stakeholders had the opportunity to share their perspectives on the final decisions;
- **Evaluation and monitoring** – The maritime spatial plan was reviewed based on a proposal from the Danish Maritime Authority to increase the offshore energy and biodiversity targets in the national MSP. An agreement on the new targets was reached by the Danish Parliament in the summer of 2023. No later than 4 years into the planning period, the parties will be invited to a discussion of the maritime spatial plan, including on the basis of an increased database, the upcoming raw materials plan, the recommendations of the Fisheries Commission, the EU Commission's initiatives in this area, the ongoing offshore wind screening, developments in CO2 storage and experiences with coexistence. These initiatives demonstrate a degree of reactionary learning to accommodate for previous failures in establishing integration between sectors.

DOUBLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Data infrastructures** – In 2017, a new Maritime Spatial Data Infrastructure (MSDI) was established. The purpose of the MSDI is to make marine spatial data easily accessible and available for comparison and exchange between maritime authorities. The MSDI includes the best available data from the relevant maritime authorities and is updated as regularly as possible. In addition, the MSDI provides information about the data (metadata), such as when the data were last updated, how they are collected, how you can access the data, and the quality of the data. A separate MSP Platform was also created in parallel to the MSDI, and many of the MSDI's functions are also included in this platform. The MSP Platform forms a key basis for the maritime planning process in the WBS region, while the MSDI provides a shared platform for relevant authorities' administration of the sea areas;
- **Integration of fisheries management and MSP** – Greater integration of fisheries management in German MSP processes is shown by the upcoming MSP plan of Mecklenburg-Vorpommern. The plan includes spawning grounds within and outside of the Greifswalder Bodden. A number of areas have been marked with the legal status of a 'restricted area for the protection of fisheries resources'. This means that the safeguarding of spawning conditions is given particular weight in comparison to other competing uses. This sets a precedent for how MSP could try more often to integrate scientific knowledge on the management of ecosystem components in the region.

TRIPLE-LOOP LEARNING

- There is no clear evidence of triple-loop learning occurring or examples that suggest it is feasible in the near future. Whilst some examples of collaboration are beginning to emerge, a continued lack of transboundary

cooperation presents a major obstacle to developing greater adaptive governance practices.

CHALLENGES TO CHANGE

- **Lack of resources** – The insufficient resources in the designation of protected sites have posed significant challenges in implementing and monitoring these areas. Budget issues remain a very real barrier to achieving all European goals and strategies;
- **Transboundary cooperation** – There remains limited transboundary cooperation when identifying priorities and developing specific objectives for the WBS region. Additionally, there has been a lack of cross-border consultation of these objectives to regional stakeholders or definition of mutual environmental issues within the region;
- **Political will** – Examples of successful change across the WBS governance regimes have been dependent on the government drive to restructure governance processes. However, there remains a lack of commitment to fully address some issues. Without the political commitment to initiate action, the capacity of more adaptive frameworks is likely to be significantly lower.

4.8 Western Mediterranean Sea

OVERVIEW OF EXISTING GOVERNANCE REGIME

The WMS Planning Site has an area of about 846,000 km², and it includes EU and non-EU countries (Europe and North Africa). The region is subjected to intense and widely spread human pressures, including high commercial fishing and large discarding and by-catch rates of non-commercial and vulnerable species. Additional management challenges include climate change effects, such as intense sea warming and ocean acidification, as well as habitat degradation, pollution and the introduction of invasive species. In the WMS, there are several simultaneous sectorial processes taking place with relevant implications in terms of MSP, but there is not currently any MSP that covers all blue economy activities and conservation. Regarding EBSA, there are two transnational EBSAs already defined, yet they are not directly applied to management purposes. There are also two transnational FRAs implemented in the Western Mediterranean Sea with concrete management plans in place. There is an increasing perception in the basin of the need to develop MSP, but the general perspective is that first it should be reinforced at the national level, while at the international level, the next step forward in the short term could be in agreeing common data collecting frameworks, continue working on sectorial spatial marine processes and agreeing on common political goals. Transnational global MSP processes are only considered in the long term.

IDENTIFIED GOVERNANCE PROBLEMS

- **Biodiversity** – Habitat degradation, pollution and the introduction of invasive species (e.g., blue crab) are creating significant challenges for the sustainable management of biodiversity in the WMS region;
- **Transboundary cooperation** – National plans are still in their first steps in some countries and they do not exist yet in others. There is no regional MSP structure that covers the WMS as a whole, although countries do participate in the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM). Through the GFCM, some fisheries regulations and FRAs have been agreed. Despite this, most of the MSP in the WMS region is done at the national level. As a result, many stakeholders consider that the national MSP and MPA processes provide them with necessary environmental information, limiting their desire to engage with transboundary policy processes;
- **Policy complexity** – Complexity and fragmentation of the legislation exist regarding the issues that MSP has to consider. There is no legislation that encompasses the protection of marine ecosystems across the region, nor is there a general marine law that can guide transboundary cooperation. Whilst the UNCLOS is a unique law regarding marine issues, it is too general and it lacks specific guidance regarding MSP or MPAs processes across nations;
- **National MPAs** – Considering all MPAs in this Planning Site and management plans associated with them, it can be observed that they are designed and implemented starting from the national perspective interests, not from a basin analysis perspective;
- **Consultation** – Stakeholder participation is considered rigid and not enough to properly address positively and constructively the concerns of some of the stakeholders. In some occasions, stakeholder participation is too reactive and starts to be actively involved, once the decision is in the last stages so changes are more difficult to introduce. In non-European national MSPs and MPAs participation processes are more limited, stakeholder influence is structured and the participation of social stakeholders is lower.

HOW STAKEHOLDERS ADVOCATE FOR CHANGE

- **Formal transboundary consultation** – In all the national MSP processes, the transnational perspective is introduced through formal consultations with national neighbours' administrations, as part of the environmental strategic consultation process. These processes provide a formal structure for transboundary engagement and communication;
- **Transboundary initiatives** – As far as transboundary cooperation is concerned, it is important to mention the WestMED Initiative, where different countries (Algeria, France, Italy, Libya, Malta, Mauritania, Morocco, Portugal, Spain and Tunisia) collaborate in the context of the development of the blue economy. It is an initiative that is supported by the EU with the support of the Union for the Mediterranean;
- **Advisory council** – In the WMS region, eNGOs regularly engage with different actors through collaborative activities. For example, in the fisheries sphere, the Mediterranean Advisory Council (MEDAC) is made up of European and national organisations representing the fisheries sector (including the industrial fleet, small-scale fisheries, the processing sector and trade unions) and other interest groups (such as eNGOs, consumer groups and sports/recreational fishery associations) which operate in the WMS area;
- **eNGO coalitions** – Some eNGOs in the WMS region, including Oceana, have developed coalitions with other lobbying organisations. Unlike WWF or GreenPeace, Oceana does not have a public-facing campaign. Instead, they provide direct expertise to policymakers and often utilise the media to expose emerging issues. This work is regularly done by acting in alliance with other eNGOs. Such a collaborative approach demonstrates growing levels of coordination between organisations in the WMS when attempting to amplify specific messages and strengthen how change is advocated for. Coalitions are shown to support reflection amongst eNGOs and to enable common understandings to develop.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY OF GOVERNANCE

In the WMS region, there is growing evidence of new approaches being designed and implemented to address governance challenges. This provides hope that the region can efficiently develop more sustainable and adaptive governance practices. There are many examples of change that represent single-loop learning, including the implementation of new shipping measures that will support conservation across the Mediterranean, as well as the alignment of policy revision timeframes. There is also evidence double-loop learning occurring within the governance regime, with alternative and innovative protection areas being designed – with significant input from eNGOs in this process – a key example of this. Additionally, the creation of new transboundary political agreements, added to the development of a 'community of practice' initiative, will play a significant role in mitigating previously identified governance challenges. Other instances of learning in the region relate to changes to wider governance processes, such as revised participation processes and a shift toward bottom-up initiatives for co-developing FRAs.

SINGLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **New shipping measures** – The International Maritime Organization is in the process of approving the 'North Western Mediterranean Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas' management plan, which will introduce specific shipping restriction measures on both regional SPAMIs, in a coordinated action of Spain, France, Italy and Monaco, to protect marine mammals;

- **Evaluation** – There is an increasing effort to better evaluate the international FRAs already defined in the basin. In 2023, the GFCM defined guidelines for minimum monitoring and evaluation processes to be implemented in all Mediterranean FRAs. They will try to overcome some previously detected limits, for example, not all the FRAs had a specific monitoring program, and sometimes they did not have a regular evaluation of their success in achieving FRAs objectives. As a consequence, their evaluation was done on an ad-hoc basis which, at times, did not comprise sufficient information. The new FRAs procedures include regular revisions of the results, clear monitoring systems and adopting a more adaptive approach;
- **Aligning timeframes** – Efforts have been made to align the timings of the next revision of the MSP with the Marine Strategy Directive Good Environmental Status (GES) report. They consider that there are very important synergies between both processes in terms of data gathering and that it will help to ensure that MSP is adapted to support the implementation of GES;

DOUBLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Alternative protection measures** – The design and implementation of FRAs within the WMS region will play a key role in restoring essential fish habitats and achieving 30% protection before 2030. There are two transnational FRAs implemented in the WMS, with concrete management plans in place, the ‘Gulf o Lions’ FRA – where both France and Spain’s interests are affected – and the ‘below 1000m depth’ FRA – relating to all countries in the region. They are currently both under review with the aim of increasing the level of protection. There is also a new FRA being evaluated at the Morocco-Algerian-Spanish frontiers. In the context of the Barcelona Convention, the countries established a list of SPAMIs. Most of them are small and nationally based, but two of them are of regional interest, the ‘Pelagos Sanctuary for the Conservation of Marine Mammals’ (with French, Monaco and Italian interests) and the ‘Cetaceans Migration Corridor in the Mediterranean’ (at Spanish EEZ International waters but with regional relevance). It is also worth noting that eNGOs played a significant role in the development of some of the FRAs in the WMS region. For instance, Oceania, in collaboration with other organisations, publicised the failings of previous protection initiatives and provided knowledge to support calls for FRAs to be implemented in their place;
- **New stakeholder platforms** – The Mediterranean Blue Economy Stakeholder Platform (MedBESP) – previously known as Virtual Knowledge Center – is a regional networking platform for sharing knowledge and supporting the development of the blue economy. It online a web-based portal aimed at providing a systemic and coherent framework to improve maritime governance in the Mediterranean by promoting and achieving a more strategic, integrated and coordinated approach to policies and actions impacting the sea. MedBESP also facilitates inter-systems cooperation and synergies across sectors and borders at regional, sub-regional and national levels. It has also enabled the development of a common and coherent framework to enhance the exchange and dissemination of knowledge, networking and capacity-building;
- **Political agreements** – The WestMED initiative is a new political agreement that focuses on promoting MSP in the WMS region. This comes from a bottom-up approach, whereby national governments from Spain, Italy, France and the Southern Basin Countries (Morocco and Algeria) engage with each other regarding collaborative data-gathering approaches and the identification of common challenges. In the context of the WestMed initiative, there is a five-

year evaluation process that includes the evaluation of all their processes and objectives;

- **Community of Practice initiative** – The MSP Community of Practice (CoP) in the Med is an initiative aimed at establishing permanent communication and dialogue across borders. This involves exchanges between experts on MSP (i.e. planners, technical experts, and researchers), and the communication of knowledge and relevant experiences in the region to reach a shared perspective on topics of common interest. It has also enhanced the cooperation between the north and the south of the Mediterranean. The main two topics of common interest for the CoP are MSP as a key enabler for the implementation of national Sustainable Blue Economy strategies and initiatives, and MSP supporting the extension and improved management of MPAs and OECSs in the WMS.

TRIPLE-LOOP LEARNING

- **Bottom-up approach** – The GFCM provides an interesting case of a technological bottom-up approach, wherein any stakeholder can suggest the creation of an FRA at the technical level. A formal procedure has been established, with stakeholders provided with a template to complete. Any proposal is discussed at the technical level and, if it is considered meaningful from the technical perspective, it will be communicated to the political level where it will be discussed and accepted, modified or rejected. This is a significant step toward the co-development of protected areas in the WMS and indicates a transformation of how stakeholders can engage with and contribute to governance actors.

CHALLENGES TO CHANGE

- **Transboundary management** – There remains a clear division within the WMS region in terms of each respective nations' capacities and involvement in decision-making. A key challenge at the basin level is the integration of all the processes at a regional or transboundary scale since there is a low level of integration between international transnational institutions planning processes;
- **MSP** – There is an increasing perception in the basin of the need to develop MSP, but the general perspective is that first it should be reinforced at the national level, while at the international level, the next step forward in the short term could be in agreeing common data collecting frameworks, continue working on sectorial spatial marine processes and agreeing on common political goals. Transnational global MSP processes are only considered in the long term;
- **Role of eNGOs** – It is noted that, when it comes to policymaking in the WMS region, eNGOs have tended to overperform in terms of advocacy. The expected role and contribution of eNGOs have grown to be greater than their resources can enable. As they participate in multiple projects, consultation processes and alliance networks, some eNGOs state that they are faced with fatigue and burnout;
- **Political will** – Examples of successful change in the WMS have been dependent on individual governments' drive to restructure governance processes. However, there remains a lack of commitment to fully address some issues, particularly those that are transboundary by nature. Without the government's political commitment to affect action, the capacity of new protection frameworks is likely to be significantly lower.

5. Discussion

By assessing how change and learning occur across governance processes, this report presents an overview of the current adaptive capacity of marine governance across multiple European regions. Information is presented regarding the current progress of the governance regimes related to MarinePlan's eight Planning Sites. Key trends regarding governance problems across the sites include limited resource capacity to conduct key governance tasks, instances of bias and power imbalances within participation processes, low levels of transboundary cooperation, and 'silo thinking' across government departments. Advocacy approaches vary across the Planning Sites, with some cases of coalitions being developed between eNGOs and marine sectors. There is also evidence of advocacy being conducted via environmental campaigns, working groups and committees, and the implementation of formal partnerships between eNGOs and governments. More innovative approaches to advocacy include eNGOs taking legal proceedings against governments for their inaction and failure to maintain legislative objectives.

The adaptive capacity of the Planning Sites varies significantly, evidenced by the different levels of change and learning that are identified in each region. This includes instances of single-loop learning, such as reactionary policy changes and the implementation of new measures to address emergent problems. The example of the BoB, wherein the French government introduced a one-month ban on almost all commercial fishing in the region to protect dolphins against the risk of regional extinction, is an interesting instance of this level of learning. Advocated for by three eNGOs, the Council of State ordered the government to close certain fishing areas within six months. Whilst the ban addressed a key conservation issue in the short-term, it failed to implement a long-term approach to managing the issue. This example clarifies how governance regimes, to be truly adaptive, must move beyond implementing short-term fixes. Instead, they must become capable of facilitating systematic change to governance frameworks and of developing long-term approaches in collaboration with non-state actors. Evidence of double-loop learning – including the revision of MSP and MPA processes, the implementation of new technologies, the creation of formal networks, and the development of alternative means of protection – provides an example of what this can include. Instances of triple-loop learning are less common across the Planning Sites, yet some examples are demonstrated. In the WMS, governance systems have facilitated bottom-up approaches to the creation of FRAs, whereby stakeholders have been empowered to instigate management change. This represents a significant step toward MPA co-management and indicates that a broader shift to collaborative forms of governance is occurring.

By synthesising the learning and change experienced at each Planning Site, an array of key barriers and enablers to adaptive capacity are apparent. Of the many barriers identified, hierarchical and top-down policy processes, as well as short-term and unstable political frameworks, are understood as critical issues. At the core of adaptive capacity is the notion of formalised collaboration and engagement, yet this is increasingly difficult to facilitate in governance systems that are informed by top-down structures. In many of the Planning Sites, tokenistic forms of participation have been continuously operationalised. In turn, stakeholders and sectoral actors have rarely been provided with the opportunity to continuously inform the design, implementation and management of governance activities. In such scenarios, stakeholders and sectors become frustrated with governance processes. This can negatively impact their trust in such processes, as well as their willingness to communicate and exchange knowledge. If governance regimes are committed to enhancing their adaptive capacity, the creation of more collaborative and co-managed initiatives is vital. Other institutional barriers include the issue of political uncertainty. Most Planning Site regions operate within political cycles that last between 4-5 years, meaning that political commitment to long-term policies, targets and objectives can be difficult to achieve. The problem of 'silo thinking' across governance networks is a further barrier of significance. Such a mentality is creating

fragmented communication within networks. This is seen to hinder attempts at creating greater levels of integration in institutional and policy settings. Instances of poor integration are particularly identified in transboundary regions, where there is a need to facilitate cross-border engagement. Due to competing national interests and a lack of formalised forums for transboundary cooperation, integration levels are relatively low and inconsistent in transboundary Planning Sites. Rigid or outdated policies and bureaucratic systems are also apparent barriers in some cases, as is limited funding to support technological innovation. With significant data gaps identified in many regions, some of which are directly inhibiting the implementation and revision of MSP and MPA processes, the need to financially support the utilisation of new research technologies and approaches is clear. However, some governance regimes indicate a limited commitment to realising such an objective. It is also useful to note that much of the institutionalisation of adaptation exemplified in this review remains at the early stage. Most of the successful cases of adaptive learning have been realised at the national level, although this has not necessarily been dispersed to international or regional levels. There is limited evidence of how regimes will mandate for transboundary and regional governance processes to start acting and making adaptation a central policy issue.

The findings of the Planning Site reviews also present important information regarding the factors that enable adaptive capacity in governance. These include clear institutional and legislative frameworks, as well as regional-national-international policy integration and transboundary engagement. Whilst such conditions are not currently achieved in many regions, it is clear that minimising policy complexity and supporting active integration are critical factors for adaptive capacity objectives to be realised. Additionally, inter-organisational networks and the creation of formal partnerships between stakeholders, sectors and government are key elements of progression toward adaptation. It is noted that formal partnerships and linkages within governance networks play a crucial role in enhancing communication, knowledge sharing, trust and cooperation between government and marine sectors. Successful examples of such partnerships are identified in several regions, including the Azores and the SNS regions. Establishing formal partnerships within governance networks can also help to develop new norms for governance, support transparent and accountable systems, and help to acquire buy-in from non-state actors for the creation of new adaptive measures. By enabling the active engagement of stakeholders and sectors in decision-making processes, beyond basic consultation processes, many of the Planning Sites illustrate how governance regimes can promote the inclusion of different knowledge, perspectives, and experiences. Additional enabling factors include the creation of measurable targets and implementable goals – which is a key means of transitioning away from short-term and reactionary governance approaches – as well as the training of governmental staff, and available financing for trialling innovative solutions. Training courses and other programs that develop the capacity of policymakers working in marine governance regimes are considered important, as better equipped regimes are more capable of handling the information necessary to make informed adaptation decisions. The importance of providing resources for governance actions is self-evident, yet it is important to acknowledge that sufficient resourcing does not guarantee action on adaptation. It is crucial to consider how resources will be used, how they will benefit entire networks (not just individual sectors or specific policy problems), and how technology will be utilised to address data gaps and facilitate more responsive systems.

By assessing these factors, it is evident that informed decision-making, transparency and the prioritisation of long-term objectives are key elements of adaptive governance. The findings of this report clarify how all network actors – government, stakeholders and sectors – play a crucial role in enabling adaptation. Therefore, regimes need to focus on developing greater interaction with non-state actors and facilitate their engagement in MSP and MPA process design, implementation and management. It is concluded that successful transitions to adaptive marine governance across the Planning Sites will depend on the development of tailored and context-specific co-management approaches.

6. Next steps

This Deliverable report represents the second output of WP4. The report is an insightful overview of the key enablers and barriers to adaptive marine governance across multiple European regions. The report will be used to directly inform the remaining task in Work Package 4, as well as provide vital information regarding the governance landscapes of each Planning Site that will contribute to other objectives within the MarinePlan project. The third task of Work Package 4, Task 4.3, will build on the findings presented in this report by developing realistic and implementable policy recommendations to improve the science base for EB-MSP. Furthermore, the findings presented in D4.2 regarding co-development and co-management within governance processes will contribute significant insight that will complement other MarinePlan tasks. By demonstrating how adaptive capacity varies across institutional contexts, the policy recommendations and solutions proposed by MarinePlan can be tailored to match the individual conditions of each Planning Site. These will include suggestions regarding the need to foster a political commitment to change, a shift toward co-development and co-management of protected areas, and the creation of formal collaboration partnerships. D4.2 represents not only a valuable assessment of the existing adaptive capacity of governance regimes across multiple European regions but also a vital resource that will help to inform the development of MarinePlan's practical outputs.

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